

OPERATIVE RELATIONS IN THE LAMNSO' CLAUSE

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to analyze the basic relations that exist between the major components of the Lamnso' clause. It investigates lexical computation and the two principal relations within the Lamnso' clause, relations within and between phrasal categories.

This investigation identifies Lamnso' as a noun class language. It assesses the interlocking agreement relations within the Lamnso' clause triggered by the Nominal affixes. No syntactic analysis of a clause in Lamnso' is ever valid without taking these agreement relations into cognizance.

The study splits Lamnso' verbs into two groups: the simple verbs and the complex verbs. Complex verbs take extensional suffixes while the simple verbs do not. These extensions have been critically examined to adequately analyse the internal structure of the Lamnso' verb. This thesis tackles the intriguing concept of movement structures within the Lamnso' clause.

Our investigation reveals that apart from NP-movement, Lamnso' like the Kru languages of Cote d'Ivoire (Koopman 1984, Tellier 1987) exhibits V-movement.

Also, Lamnso' has been found to be a *wh*-in-situ language in the likes of Chinese and Japanese (Hou, 1987).

This work adopts Pollock's (1989) interpretation of the INFL as 'split' and Chomsky's (1991, 1992) AGR-S" and AGR-O" for a proper analysis of Chomsky's universal clause structure, which fails to accommodate the Lamnso' clause. This study therefore proposes an articulated clause structure for Lamnso'.

The present work is cast within the Minimalist Program of Chomsky (1991, 1992, 1995 and other work) which is an update of the Principles and Parameters framework. As a major contribution, the study evaluates the adequacy of the Economy Principles within minimalist conceptions. It critically examines the workings of Operation Select, Operation Merge and Operation Move; within the 'working area' of the Chomskyan computational system in the light of Lamnso' derivations. This research work points out that Chomsky's Operation Select must of necessity be made sensitive to affix function in Lamnso', if output structures are to attain convergence. In addition, the work proposes that the various operations of the

working area must obligatorily be Agreement (AGR) governed towards the computation of Lamnso' phrases lest such derivations crash. This work claims further that the Conceptual-Intentional interface (C-I) and the Articulatory-Perceptual interface (A-P) must recognize and distinguish the affix function in Lamnso'. Furthermore, these interface levels must be AGR sensitive, if they are to function adequately for Lamnso' and Lamnso'-like languages.

This study therefore suggests that the operations of the working area and the interface levels of the Chomskyan computational system be parameterized to accommodate the idiosyncrasies of given languages within our concept of Universal Grammar (UG).

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by **Mr. LENDZEMO, Constantine Yuka** in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.

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LIST OF GLOSSES AND ABBREVIATIONS

N	noun
V	verb
Adj	adjective
P	preposition
TNS	tense
INFL	inflection node
Det/D	determiner
Numb	Number
N ₀	Numerals
AGR	agreement
AGR-S	subject agreement element
AGR-O	object agreement element
spec	specifier
PRM	previous reference marker

AM	associative marker
PERF	perfective
Imperf	Imperfective
FUT	future
Pres	present
PAST	past
Incept	Inceptive
PAST + Immd.	Immediate Past
NP/N"	noun phrase
VP/V"	verb phrase
PP	prepositional phrase
AP	adjectival phrase
AGRP/AGR"	agreement phrase
TNSP/TNS"	tense phrase
ASPP/ASP"	aspect phrase

CAUSP/CAUS"	causative phrase
DP/D"	determiner phrase
CP	complementiser phrase
sing	singular
pl	plural
1 st	first person
2 nd	second person
3 rd	third person
t	trace
e	empty, zero object
∅	phonetically realized as zero
H(ˊ)	high tone
L(ˋ)	low tone
LM	low mid
HM	high mid

M	mid
V	long vowel
UG	universal grammar
GB	Government and Binding Theory
LGB	Lectures on Government and Binding Theory
PP	Principles and Parameters framework
MP	Minimalist Program
PF	Phonetic form
LF	Logical form
CHL	computational system
A-P	articulatory-perceptual interface
C-I	conceptual-intentional interface
Trans	transitive
L	any given language
Intran	intransitive

X	any lexical category
X'	intermediate projection of any lexical category
PRO	null argument
Q	thematic, theta
*	ungrammatical
α	alpha
ʔ	glottal stop
π	pie
EST	Extended Standard Theory
REST	Revised Extended Standard Theory
ST	Standard Theory

DEDICATION

TO GOD ALMIGHTY

For His Goodness and Mercies

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Preliminaries

This study sets out to examine the operative (basic) relations that exist between the major components of the Lamnso' clause. The work analyses the derivation of Lamnso' nouns, verbs and the inflectional node and exploits the agreement relations triggered by the nominal prefixes and suffixes to argue for an agreement-oriented computation of Lamnso' grammar. In addition we seek to establish the role of basic agreement relations in movement structures.

This investigation is cast within the Minimalist Program (hence forth, MP) of Chomsky (1995) which is a development of the Principles and Parameters Approach (henceforth, P & P) of Chomsky (1981). The PP itself is a culmination of the trend in syntactic theory begun in the late 1970's. The PP maintains that universal properties

of natural language grammars reflect the operation of a set of universal grammatical principles and that grammatical differences between languages can be characterized in terms of a restricted set of Parameters (Radford, 1997). The basic assumption of the PP is that unlike in the traditional sense, languages have no particular rules and no particular grammatical constructions' (relative clauses, passives, etc) except as taxonomic artifacts. Rather, there exist universal principles and a finite array of options as to how given grammatical constructions are derived (Chomsky, 1995). Every grammar, it is further assumed, consists of two components: the lexicon and the computational system (Chomsky, 1992). The lexicon specifies each item and its inherent properties which are fed into the computational system. This system generates derivations and structural descriptions whose major goal is to set the parameters of Universal Grammar (UG) (Chomsky, 1981). UG is hypothesized to be an innate property of the human mind. It is thought of as a set of assumptions about what constructions are possible in the grammar of

¹For typographical reasons, the glottal stop [] will be written in this book as a simple apostrophe. For instance, '*Lamso*' will appear as '*Lamnso*'.

all languages. Each language derives its peculiarities from the choice of specific items drawn from the properties presented by UG. The principles of UG are thus parameterized to accommodate the idiosyncrasies of each language, (Chomsky, 1981, 1992, 1995 and other work).

We argue in the chapters ahead that the various relations that exist between the principal components of the Lamnso' clause require the sharing of morphological features that are language particular. Such features which serve essentially grammatical functions (we shall discover) need to be checked within their licensing domain for the clause to attain convergence.

1.2 The Language

Lamnso' is one of the major indigenous languages of the Republic of Cameroon. It is spoken by a group variously referred to as 'Banso', 'Bansaw', 'Nso's' and 'the Nso' people'. In literal terms, Lamnso' means 'language of NSO' (people)'. The Nso" people constitute one of the largest language groups in North Western Cameroon. The 1986 census figures quoted in Chilla (1988) put the Nso' population

at about 150,000. The current population has been conservatively projected to be well over 220,000 (1995 estimates). Lamnso' is spoken in the greater part of Bui Division of the North West Province of the Republic of Cameroon. The closest neighbors to the Nso' people are: the Limbums to the North East, the Bamouns to the South East and the Bamunkas to the South West. To the West and the North West respectively are the Okus and the Nonis (see Appendix IV for maps). The surface area of Bui Division is approximately 2,300 km². This area is delimited by latitudes 5°:06" and 6°:25" north and longitude 10°:20" and 11°:05 east.

Despite the geographical spread and the number of linguistic groups with which the language has been in close contact, there is little difficulty in identifying the language of the Nso' people as unique, given its phonological and morphological features as well as its word order. So far, there has been little or no evidence to Westerman and Bryan's (1970: 123) claim that Lamnso' has many dialects. However, there is a considerable degree of intelligibility between the neighboring linguistic groups and the Nso' people, particularly the speakers of the Oku and Noni

languages. A controversy however exist as to whether Oku and Noni are dialects of Lamnso'.

There have been varying, though related arguments on the proper placement of Lamnso' on the linguistic map. Richardson (1957) places Lamnso' under Kom of the Bantoid group. Eastman (1980: 25) argues that Lamnso' can be classified as a Benue-Congo language given that it is a single member of the Grassland Bantu group of languages related to the Ndop and Kom groups. As such, he considers Lamnso' as belonging to the 'Wide Bantu' of the type which on lexical evidence belongs to the group of Bantoid languages that preserves noun prefixes and concord (e.g., TIV, cf. Williamson 1971: 264). Hyman (1980) divides the Grassfield Bantu group into Eastern and Western branches, placing Lamnso' under the Ring group, a subgroup of the Western branch. Merrit (1991) splits the Ring group into the Kom and East subgroups with Lamnso' under the East subgroup, as shown in figure 1.

1. Fig. 1

(Merrit, 1991: 36)

This study adopts Merrit's classification of Lamns'o' in figure 1 above given its simplicity and identity with the classification of Dieu and Renaud (1983). We will return to the classification in chapter six.

1.3 Previous Studies

Very little literature exists on the study of the grammar of Lamnso'. However, some amount of work has been carried out principally on the phonology of the language. Banboye (1980), Grebe (1976, 1986), Grebe and Grebe (1975) are works which attempt a description of the sound system of Lamnso' within the Segmental Framework (Schane, 1973). Yuka (1994) investigates the sound system of Lamnso' within the Autosegmental framework (Goldsmith, 1976). Eastman (1980) attempts an analysis of concord agreement in Lamnso'. Onifade (1998) explores the morpho-phonology of derivations in the language while Yuka (1997) looks at the internal structure of the basic constituents of a simple declarative clause in Lamnso'. These to my knowledge, represent the few remarkable attempts at the study of Lamnso' grammar. The Bible Society of Cameroon, in collaboration with SIL² published a translated version of the New Testament Bible in Lamnso in 1990.

1.4 Present Study

This work entails principally, the exploration of operative relations between constituents in the Lamnso' clause structure. The study adopts a morphosyntactic approach in the analysis of relations within the Lamnso' Noun Phrase (NP), the Inflectional Phrase (INFLP) and the Verb Phrase (VP). It lays emphasis on the computational idiosyncrasies of these components of the language. The work discusses aspects of movement within the Lamnso' clause. It sets out to determine those constituents that can undergo movement; the bundle of lexical features each of such constituents bear and the general characteristics of their Extraction and Landing sites³. The effect of movement on the articulated clause structure for Lamnso' of Yuka (1997) is also evaluated and the necessary revisions made. Finally, the peculiarities of computation of Lamnso' grammar and its implications to

² La société internationale de Linguistique (SIL). A research institution in Cameroon that cooperates with the Ministry of Higher Education in the study of Cameroonian Languages.

³The extraction site for a moved constituent is the position out of which such a constituent is extracted (moved), while the landing site is the position it ends up in after it has been moved. (e.g, the specifier position within the CP is the landing site for a moved operator expression).

linguistic theory are highlighted given Chomsky's (1995) approach to grammatical derivations within the MP.

1.5 Tone in Lamnso'

Lamnso' is a tone language with lexically contrasting tones. Vowel quality in our data is thus undoubtedly affected by tone.

The language distinguishes five principal tone patterns with selective pitch levels on every syllable. These tones are: the Low, the Low Mid, the High, the High Mid and the Mid. Orthographically, only the High (/) and the Low (\) tones are marked. Consider the following examples:

- 2) a) lùm `dry season'
 b) kitàm `elephant'
 c) bàr `cup'
 d) bùn `squirrel'
 e) kày `a certain person'
- 3) a) lúm `bite'

- b) **kitám** `trap'
- c) **bár** `attach'
- d) **bún** `wine store'
- e) **káy** `fence'

The low and high tones in examples (2) and (3) respectively show that tone is contrastive in Lamnso' given that it occasions change in the meaning of words that employ identical phonemic resources and an identical order of occurrence.

The mid tone and any other associated low or high tone is conventionally not orthographically marked in the language. However, a high mid tone surfaces as a high tone when the vowel that bears such a tone is lengthened. Such high mid tones are distinguished from the normal high tone in that they are marked on the first segment of the long vowel as shown in example (4):

- 4) a) **nyóo** `soup'
- b) **máakfò** `spirit'

- c) **dzáá** `road'
- d) **shiyúu** `bee'
- e) **kiliim** `but'
- f) **menjáan** `castor oil'

When a simple high or low tone occurs on a lengthened vowel, the tone is marked on the final vowel segment as in (5).

- 5) a) **liì** `fashion'
- b) **kfáá** `family'
- c) **kiwuú** `foot'
- d) **njoó** `lazy man'
- e) **kfàà** `rope'
- f) **dzáá** `give birth'

The assumption in (5 a-f) is that each of the segments of the lengthened vowel has an identical tone that is marked only on the final segment. Where two identical vowels occur consecutively and yet bear different tone patterns, such

stems are analyzed as consisting of two roots underlyingly and as such are bisyllabic⁴. Evidence of such a claim is the fact that some lexical items that have two tone patterns within a single syllable have alternate long forms in which the word surfaces as a bisyllabic word with each tone being borne by a vowel within a distinct syllable (Grebe, 1986) as shown in (6 a-d).

6)	Long form	Contracted form	Gloss
a.	kiréηréη	kirèèη	`bamboo'
b.	ηwáηwáη	ηwááη	`sugar cane'
c.	kiláηláη	kilààη	`type of cloth'
d.	sáηsáη	sááη	`palm leaf ribs'

⁴ Every syllable in Lamnso' bears a tone on the vowel segment. Our interpretation above, has its strengths on the claim that a tonal segment is an indication of a syllabic division in the language (see Yuka, 1994). It is important to note that in bisyllabic nouns with prefixes marking various classes, the contrastive tone is always on the nuclear syllable (the root) while the tone on the peripheral syllable (the prefix) is always mid low.

In (6 a-d), each of the lexical items have alternate contracted forms in which the coda⁵ and the onset of the stems do not surface. In such contracted forms, the two identical vowels occur adjacent to each other. These vowels assimilate both in quality and in length, but their tones which behave as autosegments do not assimilate. Since these juxtaposed vowels are identical, they appear like long vowels but given that each vowel segment bears its own tone, we claim that such vowels belong each to a distinct syllable and that they are distinct from lengthened vowels. Some of these vowels even bear different tonal patterns as shown below:

⁵The standard structure of a syllable is conceived of as shown below:

The onset and the coda are occupied by consonants segments which are optional. The nucleus is occupied by a vowel segment which is the only obligastory part of the syllable. Lamnso' is basically a monosyllabic language. Polysyllabic words result

- 7) a. **jwàár** `very small'
 b. **yòóy** `a type of insect'
 c. **pùúr** `cat'
 d. **tàá** `old man'
 e. **mbiir** `bell'

The tonal convention adopted for this work recognizes the high and the low tones. The High Mid tones will be marked only in an instance where the vowel is lengthened. Such a tone will occur on the first segment of the long vowel. Where two consecutive vowels each bear a different tone, such vowels will be interpreted as belonging to separate syllables. In bisyllabic nouns with affixes marking various classes, the contrastive tone will be marked on the nuclear syllable while the tone on the peripheral syllable is always mid-low and therefore not marked. An exception to this is the plural prefix maker for class 1 nouns. a- (see section 1.7 for a discussion

only when peripheral syllables are prefixed or suffixed to the nuclear syllable (Grebe and Grebe, 1975).

of the nominal system of Lamnso') which will be marked as Low (à-) because it appears stressed.

1.6 Lamnso' as an SVO language

One parameter for classifying languages is to consider the unmarked order of the major sentence elements in a simple declarative sentence of the language in question (Greenberg 1966). Yuka (1997) classifies Lamnso' under the Subject Verb Object (SVO) type of languages with the guiding constituent being the position of the predicator in the simple declarative clause in the language. SVO languages like Lamnso', English and French among others are seen in contradistinction to VSO languages like Irish and Welsh (Koopman and Sportiche, 1986).

With the integration of the complementiser (Comp) and the inflection node (INFL) into the X-bar system (Chomsky, 1981), what each language needed then, was to reorder the INFL, the subject and the verb phrase (VP), since they were represented as sisters and therefore easily reorderable as shown in (8).

8) [s' comp [s INFL NP VP]

Following the revision of the structure building apparatus of Chomsky (1981), the INFL and the VP appear as sisters but not the subject which surfaces rather in the specifier position of the new I' constituent given Pollock's (1989) interpenetration of the INFL as 'split'. The 'new I' constituent is captured in (9).

9) **[spec IP] [I NP' VP]**

Weibelhuth (1995: 62) proposes a universal hierarchical sentence structure that is capable of accommodating both SVO and VOS languages, depending on which constituents undergo movement. Consider (10).

Given Weibelhuth's conceptual structure in (10), it is possible to postulate verb movement into I and the subject NP moving into [spec I'']. Such movements result in an SVO order of constituents as shown in (11a). If only the verb undergoes

movement and the subject remains in-situ, the result will be a VSO word order shown in (11b).

11) a)

b)

The Lamnso' clause in (12) is represented by the structure in (13) construed within the concepts of the x-bar theoretic framework.

12) **bv̄əy e yí ηgwàsáη**

goat PST eat corn

'The goat ate corn.'

13)

The more general claim about (13) is that when the subject of the VP becomes the subject of the IP, such a derivation is standardly referred to as subject-

to-subject raising. (The subject is raised from Spec-VP to Spec-IP). The transformation in (13) is otherwise known as the VP-Internal Subject hypothesis. The subject NP in (13), bv̀ə̀y 'goat' moves out of V', motivated by the quest for nominative case which is assigned to it in the [Spec-Head] configuration by the tensed head, I. We will examine movement structures and the conceptual assumptions that go with it in detail in chapter four.

There exists a number of factors that may necessitate a change of word order in a simple sentence in Lamnso'. Such functional processes include: Relativisation, Focus constructions, Passivation, etc. Such changes in word order are employed principally to signal subtle communication contrasts. Some of these processes in Lamnso' are analyzed in the chapters ahead.

1.7 The Nominal System of Lamnso'

Like Fula, (Arnott 1970), Swahili (Mkude 1995, Welmes, 1973) and many other languages of the Bantu family (Hoffman, 1967), Lamnso' nouns and nominals fall under different classes on the basis of agreement between nominals operated by

concord markers which vary from one class to another. Languages with such noun class systems, exhibit a number of striking similarities even when such languages belong to distantly related groups. "Classes" are grammatical categories, patterns of agreement, marked with characteristic Bantu prefixes/suffixes. The choice of characteristic prefixes/suffixes for words that agree, is ruled by the grammatical substantive subject of the utterance, from which comes the name 'noun class' (Alexandre 1967). The principal noun classes in Lamnso' are identified by their characteristic singular and plural prefixes/suffixes (Eastman, 1980). Consider the following examples.

14)	a)	ø- fàr	à- fàr
		sing. brother	pl. brother
		`brother'	`brothers'

b) **ø-gwàgwá** **à-gwàgwá**

sing. duck pl. duck

`duck' `ducks'

c) **ø-nà'** **à-nà'**

sing. cow pl. cow

`cow' `cows'

d) **ø-kán** **à-kán**

sing. monkey pl. monkey

`monkey'              `monkeys'

e) **ø-lábá'** **à-lábá'**

sing. shoe pl. shoe

`shoe' `shoes'

f) **ø-ntòn** **à-ntòn**
 sing. pot pl. pot
 `pot'        `pots'

g) **ø-shwá'** **à-shwá'**
 sing. knife pl. knife
 `knife' `knives'

In (14 a-g), each singular noun takes a zero ($\emptyset$) prefix. Its corresponding plural form takes the à-prefix. We have chosen to classify the group of nouns with the above morphological characteristics as CLASS 1 (Cl. 1) nouns. A typical Cl. 1 will be represented as in (15).

15)

(15) shows a singular/plural prefix pair for Cl. 1 noun. An example of basic sentences in the language that illustrates our morphological structure in (15) can occur as in (16).

16) a) **audu u tsèm ∅ kán yèfon.**

audu PST shoot sing. monkey yèfon

'Audu shot Yèfon's monkey.'

b) **audu u tsèm à-kán yèfon.**

audu PST shoot pl.monkey yèfon

'Audu shot Yèfon's monkeys.'

Another set of nouns exhibit a slightly distinct morphological realization from the nouns in (14). Consider the following nouns.

17) a) **gham -∅** **gham -si**
 mat sing. mat pl.
 `mat'**                              **`mats'

b) **koi- ∅** **koi- si**
 arm sing. arm. pl.
 `arm'**                              **`arms'

c) **láv- ∅** **láv- si**
 house sing. house pl.
 `house'**                              **`houses'

The nouns in (17 a-g) exhibit neither a prefix nor suffix singular marker. However, there is a morphologically marked plural suffix marker -si. Such nouns will from, henceforth, be classified as class 2 nouns. Each of the nouns in this class must fit neatly into the structure in (18).

18)

The constructions in (19 a-b) show a Cl. 2 noun in both its singular and plural form.

- 19) a) **tata a bóm lāv- ∅ mò'ón [e pp bamenda]**
 tata PST build house sing. one in bamenda
 'Tata built one house in Bamenda.'

c) **shi- yúu** **me- yúu**
 sing. bee pl. bee
 `bee'                        `bees'

d) **shi- yùv** **me- yùv**
 sing. mouse pl. mouse
 `mouse'                    `mice'

e) **shi- sí** **me- sí**
 sing. cat pl. cat
 `cat'                        `cats'

f) **shi -nàn** **me- nàn**
 sing. bird pl. bird
 `bird'                        `birds'

g)	shi-	liv	me-	liv
	sing.	heart	pl.	heart
	`heart'		`hearts'	

Observe that each noun above takes the prefix shi- and me- for its singular and plural form respectively. We group all Lamnso' nouns that take shi- and me- prefix pairs under Cl. 3 nouns as shown in (21).

21)

(22 a-b) illustrate basic sentences in Lamnso' with Cl. 3 nouns.

22) a) lòn e té shi- n̄n.

lòn PST shoot sing. bird

`Lòn shot a bird.'

b) lòn e té me- n̄n.

lòn PST shoot pl. bird

`Lòn shot birds'

The fourth group of nouns is distinguished from the nouns in (2) by the morphological realization of the prefix and suffix markers. Examine the data in (23).

23) a) ki- yuú vi- yuú

sing. cock pl. cock

`cock'                      `cocks'

b) ki- cí vi- cí

sing. stick (tree) pl. stick (tree)

`stick (tree)'              `sticks (trees)'

c) **ki- bàm** **vi- bàm**
sing. bag pl. bag
`bag'**      **`bags'

d) **ki- tú** **vi- tú**
sing. head pl. head
`head'**      **`heads'

e) **ki- ya** **vi- ya**
sing. year pl. year
`year'**      **`years'

f) **ki- tàm** **vi- tàm**
sing. elephant pl. elephant
`elephant'**      **`elephants'

g)	ki-	wó	vi-	wó
	sing.	hand	pl.	hand
	'hand'		'hands'	

The nouns in (23 a-g) each takes ki- as its singular prefix and vi- as its plural prefix. Nouns with such prefixes have been classified under CLASS 4 nouns within the Lamnso' noun class system. (24) captures a typical Cl. 4 noun, given the singular/plural split.

(25 a-b) illustrate derivations with the direct objects being Cl. 4 nouns.

25)	a)	kila	a	bá'	ki-	cí	[e	kóv-	ø]
		kila	PST	fell	sing.	tree	in	forest	sing
		'Kila felled a tree in the forest.'							

b) kila a bá' vi- cí [e kóv- ø]
pp
 kila PST fell pl. tree in forest sing

'Kila felled trees in the forest.'

Given our morphosyntactic approach to the analysis of the Lamnso' noun class system, the general interpretation that cuts across these classes is that, the Lamnso' prefixes/suffixes represent number marking (singular/plural). In Table 1 below, which is a summary of the prefixes/suffixes of the Lamnso' nominal system, the affixes/suffixes operate as function markers to distinguish between the singular/plural of each noun in Lamnso'.

Class	Singular	Plural
Class 1	Ø	vi-
Class 2	Ø	vi-
Class 3	Ø	vi-
Class 4	Ø	vi-
Class 5	Ø	vi-
Class 6	Ø	vi-
Class 7	Ø	vi-
Class 8	Ø	vi-
Class 9	Ø	vi-
Class 10	Ø	vi-
Class 11	Ø	vi-
Class 12	Ø	vi-
Class 13	Ø	vi-
Class 14	Ø	vi-
Class 15	Ø	vi-
Class 16	Ø	vi-
Class 17	Ø	vi-
Class 18	Ø	vi-
Class 19	Ø	vi-
Class 20	Ø	vi-

26) Table I: Noun classes in LAMNSO'

Noun class	Function	Function Marker
Cl. 1	Singular	∅-
Cl. 1	Plural	à-
Cl. 2	Singular	-∅
Cl. 2	Plural	-si
Cl. 3	Singular	shi-
Cl. 3	Plural	me-
Cl. 4	Singular	ki-
Cl. 4	Plural	vi-

The claim in Table I is that the nouns in example (14 - 23) can neatly fit into four noun classes. Given the regular and consistent nature of the concord markers above, this study concentrates more on the four classes leaving aside the irregular nouns. These irregular nouns could simply be considered as a

residual group. We are tempted to accord them a class, say CLASS 5 Nouns, but their number is rather small and too insignificant to be given such a status. Maybe a good historical account of the language and an investigation into language change can enable us give an accurate account of these nouns. Such a historical analysis is not within the scope of this study.

Grebe and Grebe (1975: 6) have noted that some Lamnso' verbs may also be used as nouns. Such deverbative nouns have no inherent class to which they belong.

Class meaning is a principal characteristic of noun class languages, that is to say that a given class will consist of a specific class of nouns i.e. Classes have a primarily semantic value and correspond to an attempt at separating objects and beings into categories, each one of which corresponds to a general idea: human beings, vegetables, liquids, body parts, animals etc (Alexandre 1969).

Languages with such noun class systems tend to exhibit a number of striking similarities, even when those belonging to distantly related groups are

compared, we proceed to analyze Lamnso' nouns following some standard category parameters which have been the basis for the classification of some elaborate noun class systems. The motivation for such an analysis is necessitated by the need to determine the particularities of the Lamnso' noun class system. Consider the following parameters.

27) a) **Body Parts**

	Singular	Plural	Gloss
i)	ø-buùfu	à-buùfu	'lungs'
	ø-sí'	à-sí'	'throat'
ii)	shwin-ø	shwin-si	'leg'
	koi-ø	koi-si	'arm'
iii)	shi-liv	me-liv	'heart'
	shi-nyín	me-nyin	'buttocks'
iv)	ki-tú	vi-tú	'head'
	ki-wó	vi-wó	'hand'

b) **Instruments**

	Singular	Plural	Gloss
i)	∅-shwá'	à-shwá'	'knife'
	∅-ηgár	à-ηgár	'gun'
ii)	koη-∅	kónη-si	'spear'
	búη-∅	bánη-si	'bullet'
iii)	ki-soo	vi-soo	'hoe'
	ki-cí	vi-cí	'stick' (tree)
iv)	shi-ηkà'	me-ηká'	'firewood'
	shi-ghàn	me-ghàn	'musical instrument'

c) **Animals**

	Singular	Plural	Gloss
i)	∅-ná'	à-ná'	'cow'
	∅-puúr	à-puúr	'cat'
ii)	bv̀̀y-∅	bv̀̀y-si	'goat'

	jwí-ø	jwí-si	`dog'
iii)	kitàm	vi-tàm	`elephant'
	ki-liím	vi-liím	`bat'
iv)	shi-yùv	me-yùv	`mouse'
	shi-tèr	me-tèr	`squirrel'

d) **Insects**

	Singular	Plural	Gloss
i)	ø-tén	à-tén	`calabash borer'
	ø-màr	à-màr	`grasshopper'
ii)	nsòy-ø	nsòy-si	`beetle'
	ngò'-ø	ngò'-si	`termites'
iii)	shi-yúu	me-yúu	`bee'
	shi-nsér	men-nsér	`house'
iv)	ki-lií	vi-lií	`ant'
	ki-fàr	vi-fàr	`mosquito'

What the data in (27 a-d) reveals is that one has to be very cautious in ascribing any semantic correlates to Lamnso' noun classes, given that all the nouns from different noun classes can easily be represented in any isolated group of nouns. Caution is necessary because a critical examination of noun groups will reveal that liquids will generally take the plural prefix marker for class 4 nouns.

Examine the following data:

28)	me-ns̀	`blood'
	me-ntiy	`spittle'
	me-ɔgvɔr	`oil'
	me-ndzɔ́v	`water'
	me-lú'	`wine'
	me-jiíyiy	`urine'

Notice however, that the singular prefix marker for the nouns in (28) do not exist, except when referred to in terms of their containers, (e.g., a drum of oil, a calabash of wine, a cup of water, etc.). Such a reference will be ascribed the singular prefix marker shi-. One should quickly note, however, that the singular

prefix marker here is in reference to the container per se, and not the liquid content noun in question since liquids have the feature [-count].

Our general claim in the analysis of Lamnso' prefixes and suffixes has been that they function to distinguish number. There is however a noun class marker that can be said not to mark number per se. Consider the following nouns:

29)	ntòn	shi-nton	à-ton
	`pot'	`tiny pot'	`pots'
	nà'	shi-ná'	à-ná'
	`cow'	`a tiny cow'	`cows'
	koi	shi-koi	koi-si
	`arm'	`tiny arm'	`arms'
	jwí	shi-jwí	jwi-si
	`dog'	`small dog'	dogs
	yúu	shi-yúu	me-yúu
	`bee's	`a bee'	`bees'
	wiy	shi-wiy	vi-kiy

`woman'

`little woman'

`women'

The curious thing about data in example (18) is that nouns said to be either class 1, 2, 3 or 4 seem to acceptably take the shi prefix which we analyzed in Table 1 as the exclusive singular prefix marker for class 3 nouns. What the data further reveals is that the shi- prefix marker functions to denote diminutives. One could suggest that the seemingly random affixation is necessitated by the need to avoid Class conflict. Thus where a noun takes a shi- 'diminutive' marker, it has to shed its inherent Noun Class. Put differently, it comes pre-specified, as we say in phonology. Eastman (1980: 39) has also shown that diminutive reference in Lamnso' can be realized by reduplicating the root morpheme of the noun as shown in the following examples:

- | | | |
|-----|--------------------|---------------------|
| 30) | shi-tóntón | me-tóntón |
| | `very tiny pot'    | `very tiny pots' |
| | shi-ntá'ntá' | me-ntá'ntá' |
| | `very small chair' | `very small chairs' |
| | shi-tiytíy | me-tiytíy |

`very small stone'

`very tiny stones'

In example (24), we noticed that nouns that take the plural prefix marker vi and a corresponding ki- singular prefix marker belong exclusively to class 4 nouns. The following data, however shows that nouns from other classes can acceptably take the vi- prefix marker. Consider the following nouns:

31) ø-rím	à-rím	vi-rím
`witch'	`witches'	`witchcraft'
ηkár-ø	ηkár-si	vi-ηkár
`friend'	`friends'	`friendship'
ø-jín	à-jín	vi-jín
`bride'	`brides'	`marriage'
ø-fón	à-fón	vi-fón
`chief'	`chiefs'	`royalty'
wiy	vi-kiy	vi-kiy

`woman'

`women'

`womaliness'

vi-bán

`hatred'

`vitsə'

`inheritance', `night'

viwir

`pomp'

From the data above nouns from other classes are made to refer to abstract qualities by the use of the vi- prefix. What the data in (29 - 31) seems to suggest is that there is no regular morphologically marked class for animate nouns. In general therefore, we can convincingly state that there is no strong evidence that each Lamnso' class is semantically based though we have identified the shi-/me- prefix for class 4 as denoting `smallness', but we also noticed that nouns from other classes can acceptably take these prefixes. The vi- prefixes generally mark `abstractness' though again, nouns from other classes feature in this group. It may be the case that class 4 prefix markers have the capability of being generalized throughout the

Lamnso' concordial system. One could suggest that that the rather random affixation is necessitated by the need to avoid class conflict. Where the noun takes a shi 'diminutive' marker, it has to shade its inherent noun class. It becomes 'pre-specified' so to say.

1.8 The Data

The Lamnso' in this work is that used by native speakers in their everyday transactions; such as conversation, writing, broadcasting, teaching, preaching, trading, etc. Some of the data comes from both published and unpublished materials. As a native speaker, I provided some of the data, which were further verified by other native speakers.

CHAPTER TWO

FROM GOVERNMENT AND BINDING TO MINIMALISM

2.1 Preliminaries

This chapter presents current attempts in the development of concepts of derivations and well-formedness. It traces the various theoretical insights that have led to the development of the MP of Chomskyan linguistics which is an extension of the P&P framework to syntactic theory, traditionally referred to as the Government and Binding Theory (henceforth, GB) (Chomsky, 1981). GB itself is an extension of Transformational Grammar (TG) and the Extended Standard Theory (EST) model of analysis of Chomsky (1965). Since this study adopts the Minimalist approach to grammatical analysis, it is necessary that we have a good grasp of the theory itself and its antecedents. Our remarks will thus not only be schematic and selective, but will abundantly draw from hindsight. This study assumes the readers familiarity with the antecedents of the MP.

2.2 Previous Approaches to the Principles and Parameters Approach

Generative Grammar is conceived of as a formal and explicit set of rules which are adequate enough to reflect the representations that underlie grammatical sentences in a natural language. It characterizes the native speakers' knowledge of his language. In addition, it is a formally precise grammar whose empirical predictions follow from its rules and postulates (Weibelhuth, 1995).

The publication of Aspects of the Theory of Syntax in 1965 brought with it the Standard Theory (ST) which redefined the framework of syntactic research. the organization of the grammar within the ST is as in (1) adapted from Cowper (1992:6).

1) Fig. II:

The Organization of the Grammar within the S.T.

In (1), the Base component receives lexical insertion rules and phrase structure rules, which apply to lexical items taking account of their context of occurrence. The Deep-structure level is a level at which lexical items receive an input of the transformation semantic and transformational components. What to note about this model of analysis is the implicit claim that the applications of transformations depend solely on the basis of the Deep Structure. In other words, transformations do not affect the meaning of a sentence (Katz and Postal, 1964). What came to be known as the 'Katz - Postal Hypothesis' was the understanding that, transformations do not change the inherent meaning of a derivation from the D-structure to the S-structure. To achieve this many dummy nodes were employed in the D-structure to trigger transformations.

The Extended Standard Theory (EST) was a revision of the ST, with a view to redressing the problems raised by the level at which semantic interpretation takes place. The EST, then linked syntax and semantics and the two became intertwined. i.e. meaning could be interpreted at the D-structure and S-structure levels.

The semantic and the syntactic components were later separated with each operation as an autonomous system. Now, syntactic rules made reference only to syntactic information, while information of co-reference (for example) referred only to semantic information (Jackendoff, 1972). This model that preferred the autonomy of syntax was termed, the Revised Extended Standard Theory (REST).

There was need to constrain the operations of transformation, since they tended to overgenerate structures. In Chomsky's (1981) fairly recent formulation of grammatical derivations, these transformations have been reduced to a single rate

'move- α ' (move alpha); which simply moves a constituent in the only permitted manner to another slot in the clause, leaving behind a trace at the extraction site. This model popularly referred to as Government and Binding Theory (GB) is conceived of as a composite of autonomous subsystems; with one subsystem generating an output for another system (Lasnik and Uriagereka, 1988).

GB provides for a specific set of concepts (modules) which act as filters on how two or more grammatical properties can interact. Highly modularizing grammatical information has the advantage that it allows us to isolate grammatical properties (which do not interact directly in any language) from each other. These modules specify the well-formedness conditions of derivations. Grammatical information is localized. This localization of information is ensured by specifications at what stage of a derivation a particular principle can apply and at what level of representation (see the levels of representation in (2)).

At the D-structure level of representation, the Projection Principle, and Theta Theory are the general principles that determine a well-formed D-structure derivation. A transformational operation orchestrated by a single rule (move α) is the link between the D-structure and the S-Structure levels or representation.

At the S-Structure level of representation, the Case Filter, Theta Criterion and the Empty Category Principle are the principles that ensure that structures at this level are well-formed.

The LF and the PF make up the interpretive components of the grammar. Here, the PF component is associated with the audio-perceptual properties of an utterance. Phonological rules in addition to low level transformational processes like

deletion and contraction are considered at this level of representation (Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:1). The LF is an intermediate component between the S-Structure and the semantic representation (Haegeman 1991:45). The LF should be seen as a subpart of the general theory of meaning. The S-Structure is mapped into the LF representation via $\text{move-}\infty$. The Projection Principle, the Control Theory, the Binding Theory, the Theta Criterion and the ECP operate to guarantee well-formed structures.

This brief summary of the organization of grammar within GB conceptions is captured by (2) below.

Binding Theory
Projection Principle
Control Theory
ECP

2). Fig III: The Organization of Grammar within GB

The structure in (2), which is adapted from Sells (1985:24) has been variously modified by Chomsky (1981) which has been variously modified by Chomsky (1982, 1986(b), 1991, 1992 and 1995); Abney (1987), Pollock (1989) among others.

Yuka (1997) has made an attempt to demonstrate the application of the various modules of GB to Lamnso' with particular interest on how the theory accommodates the idiosyncrasies of the language.

GB itself has been further developed in the most recent theoretical model of grammatical analysis referred to as the Minimalist Program (MP). The MP is a continuation of the move from specific grammatical rules to general principles that coexist to explain syntactic phenomena (Marantz, 1995). It is distinct from GB in its assumptions that derive well-formed structures. These include:

a) Marantz (1995) describes GB as:

"... the most ambitious research project in the history of Generative Grammar, perhaps of all linguistic theorizing till date"

The too ambitious generating capability of GB did not seem to favour the quest for an enriched base component on which the concept of 'generation' was centered given that transformations (Chomsky, 1965) were only a means to an end. Thus if grammatical derivations were this end, the lexicon appears to be the proper place to explore. In the MP, Chomsky (1991, 1992, 1995) employs 'bare essentials' to derive grammatical structures within his computational system which employs

economy principles to evaluate such derivations. These principles 'check' the too ambitious generating capability of GB.

b) Chomsky's (1981) four levels of representation of classical GB (the D-structure, the S-structure, the PF and the LF levels, shown in (2)) have been reduced to only two interface levels within the MP. The Conceptual-Intentional (C-I) interface and the Articulatory-Perceptual Interface (A-P) (see section 2.3 for details). The D-structure and the S-structure levels (shown in (2)) do not feature in the organization of grammar in the MP.

3) Fig IV.

T-Model

c) In the standard GB theory, a specific set of concepts and conditions of co-occurrence are a subpart of grammar. This necessitates that grammatical derivations rely very much on the interpretation of relations for well-formedness; (for instance, Binding Theory). The weakness of such a mechanism lies in the fact that it depends on ones ability to identify the said relations. Conversely, the derivations in the MP are governed by a few Economy Principles that compare lexical resources at the

input stage with their derivational output; less economic derivations are blocked. This is contrary to GB derivations whose grammaticality depend on the properties of other structures.

Chomsky (1995) attempts to remedy the short-comings of GB outlined above and others in his latest theoretical orientation. We consider the organization of Grammar within the MP immediately.

2.3 An Overview of the Organization of Grammar within the Minimalist Program

The MP takes a cue from Government Theory and Binding Theory (Chomsky, 1981); two sub-theories that were radically modified in Chomsky's (1986b) Barriers. The MP minimizes syntactic mechanisms relying on the cheapest ways of satisfying a principle (potentially universal properties of grammatical operations or structures). Put differently it adopts the minimal approach to evaluating any derivation. To constrain an overgenerating syntax, we need principles that guide possible derivations. Such principles in the MP are matrices that compare derivations that are more nearly optimal than others (Napoli, 1996). These matrices are termed Economy Principles. The coinage here, is motivated by the idea that syntax prefers structures computed from bare essentials. Grammatically within the MP is therefore transderivationally dependent. These economy principles are:

2.3.1 Shortest Move

This is a more technically specific economy principle to subadjacency condition of Chomsky (1981). It specifies that a constituent must move to the first position of its kind up from the extraction site (Marantz, 1995). Put differently, the hierarchically closest position of the right kind from its source. Consider example (4) below:

- 4) **kila** $\emptyset$ **yí** **ré'**
 kila Non-PST eat yam
 `Kila is eating yam.'

We make the following assumptions about (4): that if we focus the verb, (5) will be derived from (4).

- 4) **yí_j** $\emptyset$ **kila** **t_j** **ré'**
 eat Non-PST kila yam
 `Eating yam is what Kila is doing.'

Notice that the derivation of (5) involves V-movement as shown below.

6)

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1. Since the argument for the Mp and its preference for bare essentials has rendered redundant the standard X-bar conceptions of Jackendoff (1977) and Chomsky (1981), it is no longer obligatory that all phrasal projections have the same structure, instead, each kind of head can project differently and constitute a phrase in itself. Following Ross's (1967) concept of $\bar{X}$ -Pruning, (6) above is simplified, given that the intermediate categories of **AGR-S''** and **TNS''** are not represented. However, we are aware of both the Endocentricity condition and the concept of Percolation, realising that the head word exercises scopal authority over all projected categories.

The verb moves from its extraction site, leaving behind a trace (t_i) and adjoins to the head TNS, forming a complex head. It is within this configuration that the head verb picks up TNS features from the head TNS. This first move leaves the TNS features of the verb unchecked and the derivation will crash at A-P (see example 9) if these TNS features are not checked. The verb then has to move again into AGR-S to check its features for convergence. The MP stipulations require that the head verb makes shorter moves each motivated by given reasons that are fulfilled at the landing site. Since this principle favours the formation of movement chains within minimal links, the relevant principle is also referred to as the Minimal Line Condition or the Minimality Condition (Radford, 1997). We return to this principle in chapter five, where we evaluate its adequacy for Lamnso'.

2.3.2 Procrastinate

This is a principle that favours derivations which halt movement until after spell-out². Procrastinate states that "if you can wait, you must wait". This principle prefers movements that do not affect the A-P over those that do. Procrastinate has been conceived of as the Principle of 'Laziness' which prefers doing nothing computationally to doing something. The understanding of the concept of laziness is that the laziest thing that could be done to a set of lexical items, is to leave them untouched in an unorganized or uncomputed pile in the working area. Lexical units

2. An arbitrary point in the Y-model (see example 9), where the derivation splits into the A-P and C-1. It's not a level on which independent derivational requirements converge. This is in contradistinction to the levels of the T-model of analysis as shown in example (1) of this chapter.

that remain unstructured within the working area until after spell-out can then benefit from a reorganization that has no impact at the interface levels. Consider the following data:

- 7) a) $[\text{whoi}_{cp}] \quad [\text{t}_{spec}, \text{killed}_{cp}] \quad [\text{what?}]]]$
- b) $*[\text{what}_{cp} \text{ did}] \quad [\text{who}_{spec, cp} \text{ kill } t_i?]$

Observe from (6a) that English (like Lamnso') has wh-movement at LF. In English, an object wh-in-situ is permitted but not a subject-in-situ as shown in (6b).

Given the superiority constraint³, the second wh- phrase what must not move overtly into [spec, cp] since it can wait, the Economy Principle of Procrastinate demands that it must wait, until LF to make its movement. (6b) crashes because what flouts Procrastinate and attempts to move when it can wait. We return to this metric in chapter five.

3. Chomsky (1973:246) defines superiority as follows:
 "... the category A is 'superior' to the category B in a phrase marker, if every major category dominating A dominates B as well, but not conversely."

2.3.3 Greed

Greed is the MP Economy Principle that ensures that a constituent only moves to check its own features. That is to say that a constituent must not move to satisfy the needs of another constituent. The movement of every constituent is motivated by selfish reasons (i.e., it is greedy). Examine example (7):

800) a) **kila_j a yiuri t_j bvəy**
 kila PST kill goat
 'Kila killed a goat.'

In (7) Kila moves from its extraction site to have its lexical features checked within the licensing domain. Within this checking relation, the element AGR ensures that both morphological agreement exist between the subject NP Kila and the entire INFL. Failure to meet such 'needs' can lead to a derivation that is uninterpretable at one interface level. Such derivations will crash.

The general assumption within the MP is that for every language (L), there exists a 'pool' of lexical resources that are drawn from the lexicon. Each lexical item is complete⁴. Constituent computation, it is further assumed, involves the combination of two lexical units for further expansion. The expanded constituent can further be expanded by the addition of yet another lexical unit. Such combinations

⁴fully inflected for case, Agreement, Tense, etc. (see Chomsky, 1995).

must hold before spell-out, failing which nothing in the A-P and the C-I interfaces can put such pieces together into a well-formed constituent in L. The organization of grammar within the MP sketched above conforms to the Y-model⁵ structure (Déchaine, 1997) in (9).

5. Generally refers has the Y-model because of the physical similarity with the orthographic structure to the letter Y; with the different that the former is upside down.

9)

Fig. V: Y-Model

⁶ This is Case Theory rebaptised as the Checking Theory.

The claims in (9) are that, the 'mother machine' remains the Computational system (CHL) whose task is to permit the possible combinations in L. The lexical resources are chosen by 'operation select' and combined by 'operation merge'. It is 'operation move' that guides every movement and its relations. We return to these operations in chapters four and five.

2.4 Specific Issues in the MP Relevant to this Study

The MP claims that an element can only move to the closest position of its kind. Thus a verb cannot move directly into AGR-S skipping over the Head TNS; (see example 5) rather, it must move first to TNS and then to AGR-S. Notice however, that the first move leaves the TNS features of the verb unchecked and such a derivation will crash⁷ at the interface level. In the chapters ahead, we set out to investigate whether the grammaticality of such a derivation is judged on the fact that TNS features of the verb are unchecked or from the violation of Greed.

Another movement issue that this study raises is why for instance, why does the NP leaves its extraction site [Spec V'] to AGR-S instead of moving into AGR-O,

7. In Chomsky's checking theory, words carry grammatical features which have to be checked in the course of a derivation. When a feature has been checked, it is erased if it is uninterpretable. Any uninterpretable features which remain unchecked and hence have not been erased at the level of the C-1(LF) will cause the derivation to crash. A derivation is said to crash if one or more features carried by one or more constituents is uninterpretable at the relevant level. More generally, a derivation will crash if any purely formal features remain unchecked. (Radford, 1997).

which is the closest landing site of the right kind to its source as stipulated by shortest move. (See NP movement in Lamnso' in chapter four). We also accord the MP's conception of the motivation for movement a closer look. Recall that in the MP, only the Head of the chain ends up in the licensing domain. Its 'tail' which is a 'ghost' (Lasnik and Uriagereka, 1988) is left as a trace unchecked at the extraction site. We accuse the economy principle, Greed, of being 'too greedy' a quality that should lead such derivations to crash on a purely theoretical plane.

Lamnso' morphology reveals categories that have complex internal structures (Yuka, 1997). For instance, the nouns and their modifiers, have prefixes and suffixes, verbs can be split into simple and complex groups.

While the INFL is a bundle of features (details of these categories are examined in chapter three). It should be interesting to subsume such complex structures in Lamnso' into the computational system of Chomsky (1995) and observe the workings of the various operation of the MP. We shall do just this in the chapters ahead.

This work's perception of agreement goes beyond Chomsky's (1995) interpretation of it as simply a relation that exists between a Head and its specifier. We argue for Lamnso' in particular that all operations within the working area of the computational system (move, select and merge) should be analyzed as agreement governed; given that selecting or merging two lexical units that lack identical features in Lamnso' produces a derivational output that fails to converge. This study thus subscribes to Amfani's (1997) concept of the 'Syntax of Agreement' i.e. where lexical phrasal and clausal computations must of necessity obey giving agreement

rules. This study employs Lamnso' data to justify such a conception in the following chapter.

2.4.1 **Motivations for the MP as a Theoretical Framework to this Study**

We have chosen to adopt the MP as a theoretical framework for the analysis presented in this study because of the reasons enumerated below:

- a) Given the Lamnso' noun class system with its prefixes and suffixes, the Lamnso' verbal system and the interlocking agreement relations between the major components of a basic clause in the language, the MP and its system of selecting lexical resources for computations in the language. The MP's elaborate checking mechanism should enable us given an empirical account of the grammaticality of phrasal and clausal computation in Lamnso'.

- b) Chomsky's (1981) suggestion that INFL houses both TNS and AGR and Pollock's (1989) counter argument that INFL is split, with TNS and AGR projecting maximally to TNSP and AGRP leads us to analyze the INFL in Lamnso' as 'split' in the sense of Pollock. We draw our inspiration from the peculiarity of Lamnso' data which exhibits morphological agreement relations between the subject NP and TNS. The element AGR ensures that the L-features of any NP in subject position must be identical with the Phi-features of any NP in subject position must be identical with the phi-features of INFL as seen in section 3.3 of chapter three. These identical Lamnso'

NP and phi-features (i.e features of person, number and gender) are checked as in the MP.

c) Convergence of derivations in Lamnso' can be judged by subjecting the various output structures under the Economy Principles of the MP. The various functional Heads of Lamnso' grammar (examined in chapter three) are subsumed under the checking Theory to avoid derivations that crash at the interface levels. Given our morphosyntactic approach to the analysis of Lamnso' grammar in this work, both morphological and lexical features of moved constituents are checked off within the licensing configuration lest they surface at the interface levels with a resultant illegitimate derivation. It is this checking mechanism which ensures grammatical derivations that has motivated our choice of the derivations that has motivated our choice of the MP as a framework for our analysis.

2.5 Summary

In this chapter⁸, we have tried to briefly trace the various theoretical developments and insights that have shaped Generative Grammar since Chomsky (1965) till date. We have examined in particular the organization of the grammar within the MP and the issues leading from there-off that are relevant to this study. In

8. The literature on the MP consists largely of debates over theoretical issues that do not look to data for confirmation as in the previous frameworks. Instead, such issues concern standards for determining what kind of theory is superior if two theories are empirically adequate (Napoli, 1996).

addition, the adequacy of the MP as a theoretical framework for the analysis in this work has been justified with claims that are examined in detail in the chapters ahead.

THE MAJOR CATEGORIES OF THE BASIC CLAUSE IN LAMNSO'; REVISITED

3.1 Preliminaries

Following Chomsky's (1981) assumption in the LGB that sentences universally expand into three categories (as in (1)): the principal components of a simple clause in

1) S $\longrightarrow$ NP INFL VP

Lamnso' have been conceived of as in (1). Yuka (1997) has attempted an investigation of the internal structure of these components in Lamnso'. In this chapter, we set out to examine and reinterpret both the internal relations within these constituents and the relations existing between the constituents given what we consider to be further insights and superior arguments to our earlier interpretations in 1997. In this study, we place the Lamnso' NP, the INFL and the VP within the larger framework of computations which prefer bare essentials as inputs to derivations (Chomsky, 1995). The discussion describes the major modifications of the post Chomsky (1981) models especially the incorporation of INFL and Det into

the X-bar theory, the VP-Internal Subject Hypothesis and arguments that are related to the projection of Functional Heads.

3.2 The Noun Phrase (NP)

Lamnso' nouns fall into different classes as shown in examples (14 a-d) of chapter one. This section reinterprets the internal relations in the Lamnso' NP: such relations are those that exist between the head noun and its modifiers. We consider nominal modification in the language in the following section.

3.2.1 Nominal Modification in Lamnso'

Nominal modifiers generally restrict the meaning of the modified noun in a given grammatical construction. Lamnso' modifiers unlike those of English-type languages are essentially post modifiers. These include Determiners (D) Numerals (Numb), the Previous Reference Marker (PRM), the Associative Marker (AM), the Adjectival Marker, etc. Yuka (1997) has shown that detailed examination of these modifiers reveal that they have prefixes which are morphologically dependent on the noun class marker of the nominal they modify.

We revisit the Determiner and the Associative Marker to justify our claims. The choice of the Determiner is informed by recent claims in the literature that the noun is subsumed within the Determiner phrase. The Determiner itself has been

interpreted as a functional element⁹ with a syntactic head that is capable of taking a nominal complement. We examine the various claims and counter claims about the Determiner Phrase shortly.

Our choice of the Associative Marker is driven by the controversial nature of its stem in Lamnso'. In addition, adjectival modification in the language obligatorily involves the AM. Finally, the morphological characteristics of the Determiner and the AM, cuts across other nominals in Lamnso'.

3.2.1.1 The Determiner (D)

The Determiner (D), as a nominal modifier has attracted the interest of analysts given the recent claims in the literature that the noun is subsumed within the Determine Phrase (DP). The D itself has been interpreted as a functional element¹⁶ with a syntactic head that is capable of taking a nominal complement. We examine the various claims and counter claims about the D shortly.

Determiners in Lamnso' are essentially demonstrative. These demonstrative determiners distinguish one noun from another by pointing out that an object is that referred to, in terms of its position and that of the speaker. Apart from intrinsically signaling the location of the modified noun, determiners also tend to distinguish

9.. A category which has no descriptive content and serves an essentially grammatical function. By contrast, a word whose descriptive content is a 'content word'. A functional category is like INFL, Comp, T.S. Agr-S, etc, whose members are functional (ie, items with an essentially grammatical function) and by extension, a category which is a project of a functional head (Radford, 1997).

nouns of different classes through their morphological characteristics. Yuka (1997) has identified the following as demonstrative determiners in Lamnso'.

- 2) $v\grave{a}n$ 'this', vin 'these',
 $v\grave{a}s\grave{a}/r\grave{a}s\grave{a}$ 'that', $vis\grave{a}/sis\grave{a}$ 'those'.

Examine the following nouns modified by some of these determiners:

- 3a) $[n'_{NP} \quad v\grave{a}n]$ $[n_{NP} \quad vin]$
 N D N D
 cow this cows these
 'this cow' 'these cows'
- b) $[n'_{NP} \quad v\grave{a}s\grave{a}]$ $[n_{NP} \quad vis\grave{a}]$
 N D N D
 cow that cows those
 'that cow' 'those cows'
- 4a) $[bv\grave{a}y \quad r\grave{a}n]_{NP}$ $[bv\grave{a}ysi \quad sin]_{NP}$
 N D N D
 goat this goats these
 'this goat' 'these goats'

b) **[bvə̀y rəsə̀]**
NP

N D
goat that
'that goat'

[bvə̀ysi sisə̀]
NP

N D
goats those
'those goats'

5a) **[shiyúu shin]**
NP

bee this

'this bee'

[meyúu men]
NP

bees these

'these bees'

5b) **[shiyúu shisə̀]**
NP

bee that

'that bee'

[meyúu mesə̀]
NP

bees those

'those bees'

6a) **[kitú kìn]**
NP

head these

'this heads'

[vitú vìn]
NP

heads these

'these heads'

b) $[[\text{kikun}_{\text{NP}} \quad \text{vis}\bar{\partial}]]$ $^{78} [\text{kikun vis}\bar{\partial}]$

 beds that beds those

 'that beds' 'those beds'

The analysis proffered for (2) through (5) is that the noun is the head of the above NP's. Such an analysis is at variance with the DP-Hypothesis of Abney (1987) examined below.

Abney's DP-Hypothesis

The assumption of Abney (1987) is that the determiner projects maximally with its head as a functional category which takes an NP complement as in (6):

The extended claims of (6) are that the D now features at all levels without skipping any intermediate levels as stipulated by the Extended Endocentricity Principle of the PP state in Radford (1990):

"Every phrase is a symmetrical projection of a single head word category, and every word category projects symmetrically into a corresponding phrase category"

In addition, Awoyale (1995) argues that D as the head of DP exercises scopal authority over the entire DP.

Ernst (1991) has however observed that Abney's arguments in (6) are weak claiming that the head D cannot be considered as a functional element. He argues that the head D fails to undergo the type of standard movements within the universal clause structure, other functional elements like the verb and TNS undergo. (eg, TNS-raising). Consider (8) below where the head TNS is raised and adjoined to the head to AGR-S, forming a complex AGR-S head which is a licensing position.

On another count, Ernst argues that, the complement of D in (6) is not a maximal projection as claimed by the DP-Hypothesis. He illustrates his claims with nominal adverbs in English.

Amfani (1996) rejects Ernst's views on the count that, the only proposal of D-movements that Ernst cites to illustrate his arguments are in French. These

movements fail to show the syntactic (overt) movement of D, instead such movements are a surface phenomenon which occur only at PF.

Amfani (1996) in turn rejects Abney's DP-Hypothesis for Hausa, given that Hausa has an idiosyncrasy phenomenon of double headedness in respect of double determiner nominal constructions.

Given that the internal structure of the Lamnso' determiner permits it to accommodate value features, we analyze this determiner as a bundle of features. Our claim is that with such features the Lamnso' D will need to be checked to ensure that its features agree with those of its NP complement. Our position in this study, therefore is that (6) is capable of handling DP constructions in Lamnso'. Consider the data below:

- 8a) [shi-yúu shi-n¹⁰]
 DP
 sing. N sing. D
 Numb bee Numb this
 `this bee'

10. Notice that the determiner comprises the locative marker -n/sà and an agreement number marker. We however refer to the entire entity as the determiner given that the agreement number marker and the locative marker function to identify the NP under modification.

b) **[_{DP} me-yúu me-n]**
 pl. N pl. D
 Numb bee Numb this
 `these bees'

9) **[_{DP} ki-tú ki-sə̀]**
 sing. N sing. D
 Numb head Numb that
 `that head'

10) **[_{DP} yi-tú vi-sə̀]**
 pl. N pl. D
 Numb head Numb that
 `those heads'

Notice that in examples (9) to (10), the prefix marker of the DP under modification. These prefixes also signal the noun class of the NP. It goes without saying therefore that the prefix of the D and that of the noun must be drawn from an identical class of prefixes given in Table 1 of Chapter one. Our argument therefore, is that as a functional element in Lamnso' the features of D should be checked within

a licensing domain to ensure convergence by eliminating those features that can cause a DP construction in Lamnso' to crash. We thus propose D-movement as shown in (11b).

11) a)

(11a) shows that an inversion of the terminal categories in (6) given the Lamnso' idiosyncrasy as a Head First language. In (11b) the NP shiyuú moves to [Spec, AGR-S''] motivated by the quest to have its lexical features checked. The D in like manner adjoins to the head of AGR-S (right adjunction) forming a complex AGR-S head which is a licensing position. It is within the configuration in (11b) that feature checking and ultimate convergence is ensured in the computation of Lamnso' DPs.

What this intrinsically means is that the adequacy of Abney's D-P Hypothesis depends on language particular idiosyncrasies. This claim draws its strength from the arguments of Ernst for French, Amfani for Hausa and our postulation from Lamnso' data. Such a conclusion is in consonance with the standard conception of U.G. and the open choices of specific items that can be drawn from it to comply to language specific requirements. After the plethora of movement (11b) can be economically represented as in (13).

(12)

In (12) the D and the class marker 'agree' and are stated once.

This study, thus adopts Abney's (1987) DP analysis for Lamnso' and analyses Lamnso' DPs following the conceptions of the MP.

3.2.1.2 The Associative Marker (AM)

Our interpretation of the Associative Marker (AM) in Lamnso' is that, as a noun modifier, it specifies the (adjectival) attributes of a given noun or a relation (of membership, possession, etc) between nouns. The AM in Lamnso' is similar to what Owolabi (1976: 35-38) refers to as "the intervening particle" within marked genitive, constructions in Yoruba. In Lamnso', the AM and N₂ relate nouns in the structure [N₁ AM N₂]. Such a construction commonly expresses possession, such that N₂ is the possessor, while N₁ is the possessed. Consider the following [N₁ AM N₂] constructions in Lamnso'.

13) Cl. 1 Nouns

- a) i) $[\emptyset_{NP}]$ ntòn w- ó shiv - $\emptyset$
- Sing. Pot sing. AM medicine sing.
- 'the medicine pot'
- ii) $[\grave{a}_{NP}]$ ntòn v- é shiv - $\emptyset$
- pl. Pot Numb AM medicine sing.
- 'the medicine pots'

b) i) [Ø-_{NP} nà' w- ⁸⁷ó Ø- krisimen
 sing. cow Numb AM sing. Christmas
 'the Christmas cow'.

ii) [à-_{NP} nà' V- é Ø- krisimen
 PL.. cow Numb AM PL. Christmas
 'the Christmas cows

14) Cl. 2 Nouns

a) i) [bvðy -Ø y- é Ø- ntàḡrī]
_{NP}
 goat sing. sing. AM sing. sacrifice
 'the sacrificial goat'

ii) [bvðy-si s- é Ø- ntàḡrī]
_{NP}
 goat pl. Pl. AM sing.
 Sacrifice
 'the sacrificial goat'

b) l) [iv-_{NP} Ø y- é Ø- kila]
 house sing. sing. AM. sing. Kila
 'Kila's house'

ii) ^á
 [iv_{NP} -si s- é Ø- kila]
 house pl. Pl. AM. sing. Kila
 'Kila's houses'

15) Cl. 3 Nouns

a) i) [shi- nân sh- é Ø- lón]]
 sing. bird sing. AM sing. lón
 'Lón's bird'

ii) [me- nân m- é Ø- lón]]
 pl. bird pl. AM. sing. Lón
 'Lón's birds'

b) [shi- liv sh- é Ø- bvər̀ə̀']
 pl. heart sing. AM. Sing. Lion
 'Lion's heart'

ii) [me- liv m- é à- bvər̀ə̀']
 pl. heart Numb. AM. pl. lion
 'Lion's hearts'

16) Cl. 4 Nouns

a) i)	$\left[\begin{smallmatrix} ki- \\ NP \end{smallmatrix} \right]$	bàm	k-	é ¹¹	lim-	ϕ]
	sing.	bag	sing.	AM	work	sing.
	'the work bag'					
ii)	$\left[\begin{smallmatrix} vi- \\ NP \end{smallmatrix} \right]$	bàm	v-	é ¹²	lim-	ϕ]
	pl.	bag	pl.	AM.	work	sing.
	'the work bags'					

(13- 16) show the AM occurring between N1 and N2. It comprises of the initial consonant of the noun class prefix which underlyingly is a copy of the nominal prefix of the noun, followed by the vowel -é. We recall from Table 1 (chapter one) that classes one and two nouns have their prefix/suffix function markers realized as zero (ϕ). In the AM, their initial consonants surface as w- and y- respectively. Our suggestion here is that the choice of these particular consonants rests on their status as open central approximants which given the position of their occurrence,

prominence is on each of the vowels that follow it, rather than on the consonant which appears to be no less than a place filler.

Assuming that we are correct, we assume further that it is because of [w], which surfaces as the AM's number agreement marker for class 1 nouns, that the AM for this class is [o] instead of [e] as is the case with other noun classes. We suggest that the rounding of [e] to [o] is occasioned by the phonological environment within which the consonants occur. y and s are the initial consonants occurring before the root of the AM, marking the plural number agreement for class 1 and 2 nouns respectively. This analysis holds for classes 3 and 4.

One could argue, however, that for classes 3 and 4 nouns, the entire prefix marker appears as the AM marker with the phonological process of progressive assimilation occurring as in (17 a-b):

- 17) a) shi + é → shé
 b) ki + é → ké

The suggestion in (17) is that when the nominal prefix and the vowel fuse through coalescent assimilation, the output is Progressive Assimilation that results in the AM surfacing as shé, ké, mé, etc. This analysis though consistent is suspect, given that it will be difficult to state specifically what the AM marker is. In addition, in coalescent assimilation, when two segments fuse, a third segment, distinct from any of the two that underwent fusion becomes the output. This is not the case in (17) where we have

$$i + \underline{e} \longrightarrow -e$$

We therefore propose the process of vowel elision for (17). The claim here is that the final vowel of the number function marker of the noun is elided as illustrated below:

$$kj + \underline{e} \longrightarrow ké$$

Evidence of our elision argument is that e surfaces as the AM marker for class 2 plural nouns that have zero for their singular prefix marker.

Yuka (1997) has differentiated between Marked and Unmarked Associative Constructions. Unmarked Associative constructions are predominant in Lamnso' with the AM occurring between the two nouns as shown in example (13) through (16). In such unmarked associative constructions, it is possible to use the AM, to refer to a noun mentioned in previous discourse. The AM in such constructions to pronominal, since it encodes the attributes of the noun it represents.

Marked Associative Constructions are distinguished by their lack of an intervening AM between the two nouns. In such constructions, the head noun cannot be omitted because there exist no pronominal AM to encode its attributes. (see section 4.2.1 for a detailed discussion of such pronominal features).

There is also a distinction between Possessive Unmarked Associative Constructions and Non-Possessive Unmarked Associative Constructions which Yuka (1997) has examined in detail.

3.2.1.3 The Adjectival Modifier (Adj)

Chomsky (1981) specifies the category Adjective (Adj) using two of the category tetrachotomy features ([+N, +V]). In addition to nominal traits the adjective carries verbal features. Consider the following adjectival modifiers of Lamnso' nouns.

17) Cl. 1 Nouns

a)	Ø-	shwà'	Ø-	-dà
	sing.	knife	sing.	long
	`a long knife'			

18)	à-	shwá'	à-	dà
	pl.	knife	pl.	long
	`long knives'			

19) Cl. 2 Nouns

93

a)	láv-	∅	∅-	-kú'òn
	house	sing.	sing.	big
	'a big house'			
b)	láv-	si	si-¹³	kú'on
	house	pl.	pl.	big
	'big houses'			

20) Cl. 3 Nouns

a)	shi-	nàn	shi-	téri
	Sing.	bird	sing.	small
	'a small bird'			
b)	me-	nàn	me-	téri
	pl.	bird	pl.	small
	'small birds'			

13. The plural of this noun in (19b) has its underlying form as shown in example (19b). When the plural form of a class 2 noun occurs with a plural adjectival modifier, their underlying forms are as shown below:

[NP [lav-si][si-kuon]]
Adj

but because class 2 nouns carry suffixes, the two number markers occur adjacent to each other. These two identical number markers conflate due to phonological economy at PF. What surfaces is [Lav-si-kú'ón] as a class 2 modified NP.

21)	a)	ki-	bám	94	ki-	bár
		Sing.	bag		Sing.	red
		'red bags'				

Examples (20) to (23) show that the adjectival modifier takes an agreeing prefix of the noun it modifies. We leave the argument occasioned by constructions that feature both the AM and the adjective for another discussion.

3.2.1.4 The Previous Reference Marker (PRM)

The Previous Reference Marker (PRM) modifies the noun it follows (Amfani, 1996). In Lamnso', the PRM follows a noun, which must have previously been referred to in the discourse. This modifier is strictly referential, hence the reason for the name, Previous Reference Marker. This noun modifier is coded by words such as vəy, siy, viy, kiy, etc. Each of these reference markers corresponds to specific noun class number agreement markers. Following our summary of Demonstrative Determiners in section 3.2.1.1, we suggest that the internal structure of the PRM is very similar to that of the Demonstrative Determiner. In other words və- of vəy, the si- of siy, the ki- of kiy, the shi- of shiy are all number agreement markers. If we are correct our suggestion then is that the PRM proper is -y. The apparent CVC structure of the PRM therefore has its CV-, marking number agreement with the noun being referred to. Examine the following examples of the PRM in Lamnso'.

24) Cl. 1 Nouns

95

a) $[\emptyset-$ **-lábá** $[v\partial-$ **y] **e** **gheén** **yula**
 NP sing. shoe sing. PRM PST fit yula
 'The shoe (referred to) fitted Yula.'**

b) $[\acute{a}-$ **lábá** $[v\partial$ **y] **e** **gheén** **yula**
 NP pl. shoe pl. PRM PST fit yula
 'The shoes (referred to) fitted Yula.'**

25) Cl. 2 Nouns

a) $[\text{shwin}-$ $\emptyset$ $[v\partial-$ **y] **e** **té** **bor**
 NP leg sing. sing. PRM PST kick ball
 'The leg (referred to) kicked the ball'.**

b) $[\text{shwin}$ **si-** **-y] **e** **té** **bór**
 NP leg pl. PRM PRM PST kick ball
 'The legs (referred to) kicked the ball'.**

26) Cl. 3 Nouns

96

a) [shi-_{NP} yuu- [shi- y]] shi I lá Vilu
 sing bee sing PRM sing. PST lick honey
 'The bee (referred to) licked the honey.'

b) [me-_{NP} yuu- [me- y]] me I lá Vilu
 pl. bee pl. PRM Numb. PST lick honey
 'The bees (referred to) licked the honey.'

27) Cl. 4 Nouns

a) [ki-_{NP} bàm [ki- y]] ki- I t ηkuy
 sing. bag sing PRM sing. PST drop latrine
 'The bag (referred to) dropped into the latrine'.

b) [vi-_{NP} bàm [vi- y]] vi- I t ηkuy
 pl. bag pl. PRM pl. PST drop latrine
 'The bags (referred to) dropped into the latrine'.

(24) through (27) shows that the PRM in Lamnso' is -y, which takes a number agreement marker that must be identical with of the noun it modifies. For classes 1 and 2, singular nouns, which have their noun prefix and suffix realized as zero, their

PRM Number markers surface as $v\partial_{-}$. Their plural counterparts take the $_{-}$, the plural number marker for class 1 nouns and the suffix $-si$ for class 2 nouns. When the two number agreement markers occur adjacent to each other, they conflate and surface as in (21b) for phonological economy.

Given the number agreement relations shown in (24) to (27), our standpoint here is that, where those number markers fail to agree, the derivation of the PRM is generally ill-formed. We provide examples in (28) to (30).

28)	*[ki- NP	bàm	[vi- y]	vi- l t	ηkuy
	sing.	bag	pl. PRM	sing. PST	drop latrine
29)	*[shwin- NP	∅	vi- -y]	e	té bor
	leg	sing	pl. PRM	PST	kick ball
30)	[me-	liv	shi- y	e	bvəràʔ]
	pl.	heart	sing. PRM	PST	lion

The NPs in (28) to (30) are ungrammatical because of the mismatch of the number prefix marker of the noun and the number agreement marker of the PRM.

(27) is schematically illustrated in (31).

Notice that in (31) N^1 C- commands PRM^1 . The constituents they dominate, C-command each other in like manner. The features of the heads of these constituents must agree in number if the NP derivation is to be judged legitimate in Lamnso' grammar.

3.2.1.5 Numerals (N^0)

Numerals are limiting noun modifiers that express the quantity of the modified noun. They are used with animate and inanimate count nouns. In English and French type languages, numbers have the characteristic of occurring before the noun, for instance:

32)	English	French
	one book	un livre
	three stones	deux chambres
	four boys	dix sacs

where one, three, four, un, deux and dix are numerals.

In Lamnso' however, numerals follow the nouns they modify. Examples of such numerals include: mò'ón 'one', baà 'two', taár 'three', nín 'several' and the indefinite wùmò 'some'. mò'ón often used to contrast the dual baà and other plural numerals. The singular numeral mò'ón takes a zero affix when it modifies classes 1 and 2 nouns respectively. Examine the following data.

33) Cl. 1 Nouns

a)	[$\emptyset$ - NP]	ntòn	$\emptyset$ -	mò'ón]
	sing.	pot	sing.	one
	'one pot'			
b)	[à- NP]	ntòn	à-	baà]
	pl.	pot	pl.	two
	'two pots'			

34) Cl. 2 Nouns

			100
		η	
a)	[bvà̀y-ø	ø-	mò'ón]
	goat	sing.	sing one
	`one goat'		

b)	[bvà̀y-si	si-	baà
	goat	pl.	pl. two
	`two goats'		

The numerals baà, taár, kweè, and tàn each takes the plural affix of nouns they modify. Interestingly, from the number ntúfú `six' and above, the numeral modifiers do not take the noun affix of the nouns that precede it. Consider the data below.

35) a)	[là-	ntòn	à-	tàn
	pl.	pot	pl.	five
	`five pots'			

b)	[là-	ntòn	ntúfú]
	pl.	pot	six
	`six pots'		

c)	[là-	ntòn	¹⁰¹ ghvə̀m]
	pl.	pot	ten
	`ten pots'		

The constructions that surface with numerals above the number 'five' are similar in structure to the Noun-Noun constructions. The only explanation we can proffer for now, for the realization of affixes with only numerals representing 'two' to 'five' in Lamnso' is that more often than not, these numerals are used in contrast to 'one' which is singular. In such constructions, the plural status of the numeral modifier is emphasized by the plural prefix. The plural status of numerals from ntúfú and above is taken as given. Nominal modifiers in Lamnso' must have a given agreement relation between the number prefix marker of the noun and the numeral modifier.

Suffice it to restate that section 3.2.1 gives us a glimpse of nominal modification in Lamnso'. We leave these issues that are computationally relevant to return to them in section 3.5 when we consider an articulated structure for the Lamnso' clause

3.3 The Inflection Node (INFL)

Chomsky' (1981:18) standard interpretation of the Inflection Node (INFL) is as in (36):

Pollock (1989) modifies Chomsky's concept of the INFL in (36). Following Abney's (1987) Functional Approach to Category Classification, Pollock argues for a 'split-INFL' with AGR and TNS, each heading a maximal projection as shown in (37):

Pollock claims that splitting the INFL into two independent projections leads to an optimal analysis of moral order (in French and English). TNS and AGR are analyzed as functional heads of their respective maximal projections.

In this section, we present TNS and ABR in Lamnso'. In addition, we reexamine the INFL in Lamnso' in the light of their heads as functional categories

given that TNS and AGR are the locus of the features against which the verbal and lexical features are judged for convergence.

3.3.1 Tense

Yuka's (1997) analysis of TNS in Lamnso' reveals that, in clauses where class 1 or class 2 nouns occur in their singular forms, the morphological nature of TNS is determined by the final vowel or consonant of the last syllable of the element that precedes TNS. With classes 3 and 4 nouns, it is the final vowel of the number agreement marker of the noun in subject position that determines the morphological nature of TNS (which surfaces as a lengthened copy of the vowel of the agreement marker). When no NP occurs in subject position, it is the final vowel of the pleonastic element (the place filler) that determines the morphology of the past tense marker. The present tense marker in the language is morphologically realized as zero ($\emptyset$). In other words, the present tense marker lacks morphological content.

The present study in addition considers the Inceptive (Incept) marker which occurs with the present tense in the language, and the Immediate Past (PST + Immd) which Yuka (1997) fails to examine. Consider (24) below:

- 38) a) **kila- $\emptyset$ yí ré' fó ntòn**
 kila Non-PST eat yam from pot
 'Kila is eating yam from the pot.'

b) **kila- ø** **si** **yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 Kila Non-PST Incept. eat yam from pot
 'Kila has (started) eating yam from the pot.'

c) **kila a si** **yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 kila PST Incept. eat yam from pot
 'Kila had (started) eating yam from the pot.'

d) **kila a yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 kila PST eat yam from pot
 'Kila ate yam from the pot.'

e) i) **kila ki** **yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 kila PST+Immd. eat yam from pot
 'Kila (just) ate yam from the pot.'

ii) **à ki** **yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 you (sing) PST+Immd eat yam from pot
 'You (just) ate yam from the pot.'

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 iii) **vén** **ki** **yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 you (pl.) PST+Immd eat yam from pot
 'You (just) ate yam from the pot.'

iv) **awune** **ki** **yí** **ré'** **fó** **ntòn**
 they PST+Immd eat yam from pot
 'They (just) ate yam from the pot.'

What the data above shows is that, apart from the Present and Past tenses, which are analyzed as discussed above, there also exist the present inceptive marker (**si**) which designates the present progressive. **si** is peculiar in that it also combines with the Past tense as in (38c) to specify actions that have been going on for some time in the past. the Immediate Past marker surfaces as **ki**. **ki** does not need to combine with the Past tense as is the case with **si**, rather it occupies the position of the tense marker. Notice from (38 (e)i-iv) that **ki** does not owe its morphological nature to the subject NP. It remains constant despite the changes in the subject NP. **ki**, it should also be noted, has no connection with any noun class prefix.

What we have referred to as Tense in Lamnso' could otherwise be interpreted as Agreement (AGR). Consider the following constructions.

kila	a	yí	106	ré'
kila	AGR	eat		yam
'Kila ate yam'				

Observe that the last vowel of the subject NP is morphologically identical to AGR i.e the subject-head determines morphological concord. However logical this argument sounds, the interpretation of TNS as AGR does not hold for the future tense as shown in example (38e)

This study subscribes to the realization of the Non-Past and Past tenses in Lamnso' as described above. For the Future tense realization, we proceed to provide a more detailed analysis motivated by empirical evidence and new insights from additional data. Our conception of the Lamnso' future tense marker had principally three realizations (Yuka, 1997) which we categorized as the Near Future (yii) and Immediate Future (lò) and the Distant Future (wiy).

Our data shows that the future tense in Lamnso' can better be subdivided into Non-Progressive (yii), the Non-Progressive yíi, the Distant Future (wiy) and the Far Distant Future (wiya).

Non-Progressive Future

The Non-Progressive Future is otherwise referred to as the Immediate Future. It refers to actions which will take place on the same day. The morphological marker for this tense is yii. For example:

- 39) a) **kila yii** **yí ré' fó ntòn**
 kila Fut+NonProg. eat yam from pot
 'Kila will eat yam from the pot.'

- b) **lukong yii** **té shinàn**
 lukong Fut+NonProg shoot bird
 'Lukong will shoot a bird.'

Progressive Future

The Progressive future designates those actions that will take place in some time to come, but specifically on a different day, given the day of the utterance. Examine the following constructions in (40):

- 40) a) **kila yii a yí ré' fó ntòn**
 kila fut Prog. eat yam from pot
 'Kila will eat yam from the pot (someday to come).'
- b) **lukong yii a dú e yaounde**
 lukong will Prog. go to yaounde.
 'Lukong will go to Yaounde (someday to come).'

The Distant Future

The distant future signals those actions that will take place in some days to come, ie, actions that will occur in a week's time per se. Consider the following data:

- 41) a) **kila wiy yí ré' fó ntòn**
 kila FUT+Dist. eat yam from pot
 'Kila will eat yam from the pot (in a week's time).'

- b) **lukong wiy dú e yaounde**
 lukong FUT+Dist. go to yaounde
 'Lukong will go to Yaounde (in a week's time).'

The Far Distant Future

This designates those actions that will occur far into the future, say in two months or more. This particular future is realized by a combination of the Distant Future Marker and the marker of the Progressive Future. Examine the data in (42 a-b).

- 42) a) **kila wiy a yí ré' fo ntòn**
 kila Fut+Dist. Prog. eat yam from pot
 'Kila will (be) eating yam from the pot.'

43)

It is within [Spec-Head] agreement relation in Lamnso'. The claim in (28) is that TNS adjoins to head of AGR-S through left adjunction.

Given the subject-INFL relation in Lamnso' we have postulated abstract agreement futures that form part of the L-features (Φ -features)¹⁴ of AGR within the INFL of a Lamnso' clause. Understandably, Lamnso' phi-features do not include the feature Gender, given that the language does not mark nor differentiate gender (see example (27 a-d) of chapter one). (44) below represents the L-features of a subject DP in Lamnso' and the 'articulated' phi-features of the element AGR.

44)

L-features of subject

$\pm$	sing.
Σ^{15}	Person

phi-features of AGR

$\pm$	sing.
Σ	Person

15. Σ is standardly referred to as sigma. It is the 18th letter of the Greek alphabet. It is commonly used in linguistics to designate an unstable element which is a bundle of features. In example (44) Σ represents either First (1st), Second (2nd) or 3rd person. In this work, the L-features of a subject DP specify feature person as either Σ^{1st} , Σ^{2nd} or Σ^{3rd} with the following interpretation:

- 1st Σ^{1st} first person
- 2nd Σ^{2nd} second person
- 3rd Σ^{3rd} third person

Number distinction is taken care of by the [$\pm$ sing] feature.

The claim in (44) is that, the L-features of a DP in subject position must of necessity be identical with phi-features of AGR for a clause to be judged grammatical. Where either the number features of the subject DP or the features of person fail to be identical with those of AGR, the clause crashes for lack of agreement. We test our claims about (44) in (45) to (46) below.

45) ki- rúḡ ki- i shwí e kíy
 Sing. yam Sing. PST burn in hearth
 'A yam was burnt in the hearth.'

46) *Ki rúḡ vi -ii shwí e kíy
 Sing. yam Pl. PST burn in hearth

The non-convergence of (46) is because there is lack of number agreement between the subject NP and AGR of INFL.

Given the concept of AGR-S and AGR-O and their role in ensuring convergence in a clause, this study views the head of AGR-S as the governor of the relationship that exists between the subject and the INFL in Lamnso'. Evidence for our claim is the various prefixes of Lamnso' nouns that surface as agreement markers. We return to the agreement features of AGR in section 3.5.2.

3.4

The Verb Phrase

Like every other maximal projection, the verb phrase (VP) is a symmetrical projection of a single head word category (V) (Radford, 1990). The VP is standardly

referred to as the 'predicate' because it contains the verb which is the sentence 'predicator' (Yusuf, 1992a). Chomsky (1986:2) distinguishes the verb as [-N, +V]. This feature neatly identifies the Lamnso' verb.

In this section, we revisit our description of the internal structure of the Lamnso' verb in order to further analyze its morpho-syntactic structure. In addition, we look at its status as a lexical item with V-features that need to be checked off before spell-out. Our arguments in this section draw their strength from the morphological classification of Lamnso' verbs. Consider the data below:

47)	a)	i)	lúm	ii)	lúm-nin ¹⁶
			'bite'		'bite each other'
	b)	i)	tóy	ii)	tóy-nin
			'accuse'		'accuse each other'
	c)	i)	mùy	ii)	mùy-nin
			'finish'		finish (with) each other'
	d)	i)	kuu	ii)	kuu-nin
			'insult'		insult each other'
48)	a)	i)	fó	ii)	fó-ri
			'give'		'give + repetitive'
	b)	i)	lúm	ii)	lúm-ri

16. As was the case with the nouns, I segment the smallest meaningful units of the lexical item with a hyphen given that the stem and its constituent parts are under special consideration. Otherwise, such words appear as single units without a hyphen.

			`bite'		
	c)	i)	kuu	ii)	`bite + repetitive'
			`insult'		kuu-ri
	d)	i)	té	ii)	`insult + repetitive'
			`shoot'		té-ri
					`shoot + repetitive'
49)	a)	i)	lém	ii)	lém-kir
			`wound'		`wound + iterative'
	b)	i)	tò	ii)	tò-kir
			`enter'		`enter + iterative'
	c)	i)	nyèṅ	ii)	nyèṅ-kir
			`run'		`run + iterative'
	d)	i)	kò	ii)	kò-kir
			`snore'		`snore + iterative'
50)	a)	i)	táv	ii)	táv-ir
			`strong/strength'		`cause to be strong'
	b)	i)	lém	ii)	lém-ir
			`wound'		`wound + causative'
	c)	i)	tún	ii)	tún-ir
			`absolve'		`absolve + causative'
	d)	i)	mày	ii)	mày-ir
			`finish'		`finish + causative'

- 51) a) i) mày
`finish'
- ii) mày-si
`finish + completive'
- b) i) rán
`clean'
- ii) rán-si
`clean + completive'
- c) tsən-si
`dispatch + completive'
- d) faa-si
`spray + completive'
- e) feé-si
`blow + completive'
- 52) a) i) 𠵹'é'
`pinch (economically)'
- ii) 𠵹'é-ti
`pinch + applicative'
- b) i) lá'
`pay'
- ii) lá-ti
`pay + applicative'
- c) shá'-ti
`greet + applicative'

'release + applicative'

Examples (33) to (38) show the various verbs in Lamnso' with their possible suffixes that capture a range of meaning extensions. These suffixes include -nin, -ri, -kir, ir, si and -ti¹⁷. The data above further show that, fundamentally, verbs in this language can be split into two groups: those verbs that take no suffix and those that take. We refer to those without any extensional suffix as the simple verbs and those with extensions as the complex verbs. We attempt an analysis of these verbal extensions. Consider the data below:

53) a) **lòn e** $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{[lém-ir} \\ \text{VP} \end{array} \right]$ **kila]**

lòn PST wound + causative kila

'Lòn wounded Kila.'

b) **lòn e lém**

lòn PST wound

'Lòn was wounded.'

c) ***lòn e** $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{[lém} \\ \text{VP} \end{array} \right]$ **Kila]**

lòn PST wound

See the appendix for a brief summary of the semantic references of these suffixes.

54) a) **audu u** **[mày-si** **mendzə̀v]**

audu PST finish + completive water

'Audu finished the water.'

b) ***audu** **u** **mày** **mendzə̀v**

audu PST finish water

c) ***audu** **u** **mày**

audu PST finish

The sentences in example (53) show that in basic clauses in the language, when a verb takes the causative extension it equally takes an object NP for a complement. Conversely, when such an extension is absent the ability of the verb to assign accusative case is neutralized as shown in (53c). This analysis applies to example (54) with the completive extension.

We are tempted by the evidence in (53) and (54) to analyze these extensions as the morphological codings (that contain the features) of accusative case assignment. We could even assume further that the causative and the completive extensions are functional heads that project maximally in the sense of Abney (1987). We assume further that for the verb to acquire the 'potency' to assign accusative

case, it has to move to get adjoined to such a functional head to pick up the needed case assignment features. Examine (55) below:

55)

The claim in (55) is that the verb moves to adjoin with the head of the causative phrase, forming a complex head. This movement is motivated by the quest to have the verb inflected with causative features. Such features can then be

checked by AGR in a subsequent move. This postulation draws its strength from minimalist conceptions.

Notice our claim for left adjunction in (55). The analysis in (55) will hold for the completive phrase as well. The features of the complex head of the causative phrase enters into a checking relation with the head of AGRP and the head of the CausP; a [Head-Head] licensing domain.

However consistent (41) might appear, especially as it seems to appropriately reflect the realities of the Lamnso' VP- internal structure, and the assumptions of the MP, this study is hesitant to readily adopt it. This is because other verbal extensions don't seem to exhibit the characteristics of the completive and the causative extensions. The simple verb that take the Applicative, the Repetitive and the Iterative extensions are inherently transitive verbs which have the potency to assign accusative case to their complements without any extensional suffix. Consider the following examples:

56) a) **audu u lá'-ti metuden**
 audu PST pay + applicative students
Audu paid the students.

b) **audu u lá' metuden**
 audu PST pay students
'Audu paid the students.'

57) a) **kila a té-ri** 120 **meǹ̀n**
 kila PST shoot + repetitive birds
 'Kila shot birds.'

b) **kila a té meǹ̀n**
 kila PST shoot birds
 'Kila shot birds.'

Examples (56) and (57) show that unlike the verbal extensions in (53) and (54), the ability of the verbs to assign accusative case does not depend on the verbal extensions.

Another approach to the analysis of these could be to consider the verbal roots principally as transitive versus intransitive verbs. Notice, however that the status of verbal extensions will still be our focus given that they seem to accord the ability to assign case with some verbs and yet their presence in others is not grammatically significant. We attempt an analysis of this phenomenon immediately. Consider the following data:

58) a) **lòn e kisi**
 lòn PST cough
 'Lòn coughed.'

b) *kibv̀̀r ki 121
 dust Numb i ḱśi lòn
 PST cough lòn

59) a) wán e buune
 child PST sleep
 'The child slept.'

b) lú_ e buune wán
 Song PST sleep child

(58) and (59) each show their (b) counterparts as ungrammatical because buune 'sleep' and ḱśi 'cough' being intransitive verbs, fail to participate in transitivity alternation as do verbs like màysi, ránsi, lúmsi, etc. which occur in constructions in which the agent is the syntactic subject in the transitive construction.

Our analysis of verbs such as those in example (53) and (54) is that they are derived from adjectives, while those in example (58) and (59) are derived from nouns. We claim further that the split between the alternating and non-alternating verbs lies on Adjective-based and Noun-based verbs. The assumption here is that the morphological derivation of such verbs is based on the combination of both verbal and adjectival features for alternating verbs, while the non-alternating verbs are derived from the verbal and nominal combination of features. Our assumptions are represented in (60 a and b).

60) a)

b)

In his standard ($[\pm N, \pm V]$) category tetrachotomy features, Chomsky (1986: 2) makes a distinction between lexical and non-lexical categories. Here the category, verb is identified as $[-N, +V]$, Noun as $[+N, -V]$, while the Adjective and the Preposition are identified respectively as $[+N, +V]$, $[-N, -V]$. The assumption in (60) then becomes fundamental, taking into consideration Hale's (1986) argument that adjectives denote qualities or states and thus are predicates which cannot function as subjects or objects. Nouns, denote entities and are not predicates. Nouns can therefore function either as subjects or objects in clauses. Our assumptions in (60) is motivated by the preceding analysis.

Supposing that our assumptions are correct and consistent (and we are certain they are) , we argue further that an adjective, as a predicate must take a subject in the $[\text{spec}, V']$ position. The NP that occupies this position is termed in the literature as the "internal argument". Taking cognizance of the fact that the verb in question subcategorizes for an argument (ie, nominal argument internal to the verb),

such an argument occurs within the V'. Adjective based verbs are represented as in (61a).

The noun based verbs fail to motivate an internal argument of the type in (61a) understandably because nouns are not predicates and will themselves appear in argument positions as shown in examples (53) and (54). This is why (61b) is an

illegitimate structure in the derivation of a sentence in Lamnso' as shown in example (58b) and (59b).

Our postulation in (61) reveals a rather interesting phenomenon; that the essential properties of Chomsky's standard tetrachotomy distinctions determines the fundamental nature of argument structure. It is the properties of these structures (call them features) that motivate movement since the noun will have to check its lexical features at its checking domain.

In example (58) therefore, the verbs kísi 'cough' and buune 'sheep' appear as verbs in sentential syntax but they acquire the status of predicates thus taking lòn and wàn as internal arguments. These arguments raise to their licensing domain where their features are checked by AGR-S of INFL. We therefore claim that, by virtue of the fact that an intransitive verb lacks an internal argument, because it is noun-based it fails to generate an argument in its [spec, V'] position. We return to this analysis in chapter four, when we consider verb movement.

3.5 Computing the Basic Components of a Simple Clause in Lamnso'

With Chomsky's (1995) vision of "the end of syntax", the computation of syntactic structures has been restricted to bare essentials. What this entails is that more attention is accorded the smallest lexical remit that is capable of altering meaning within any lexical item. Such minimal units are computed following the stipulations of specific operations within the working area of the Chomskyan computational system.

This section examines the adequacy of operation Select, Merge and Move, operations of the working area within the Chomskyan computational system. Example (9) is repeated here as example (63).

63) **shi-** **n̄n** **shi-** **n**
 N^o bee N^o this

'This bee'

Following our analysis of the Lamnso' NP, the INFL and the VP, we subject each of these constituents to Chomsky's computational 'machine' with the aim of investigating how each is computed.

Assume the following among the bunch of lexical resources found in the lexical 'pool' for a language (L): α , β , λ , π , etc. Assume further that operation select picks out two lexical units: α and β for combination towards the derivation of a given structure. Operation Merge is applied and Σ is formed. Chomsky (1995: 397) proposes three assumptions for the internal structure of Σ in (62):

- 62) a) the intersection of α and β ,
 b) the union of α and β , and
 c) one or the other of α and β .

Option (62(a)) is ruled out as untenable, given that the output conditions render such an intersection null. Option (b) is irrelevant in a situation where α and β differ in value features. Option (c) is tenable given that either α or β can project into Σ shown in (63).

In accordance with the Endocentricity Condition and the concept of percolation within the PP, the question that arises is why α and β should be computed to project into Σ . We turn to this immediately.

Our assumption in (63) is that at LF interface, Σ (maximal) gets the interpretation of a phrasal category of type α or β (as the case maybe). Following minimalist interpretation, α and β remain head units and determine Σ , its projection through strict identity. We leave the rather complicated relational arguments that have rendered redundant the standard X-bar Theory of Jackendoff (1977) and Chomsky (1981) in favour of bare essentials (Chomsky, 1995); and turn to the computation of the principal components of the Lamnso' basic clause.

3.5.1 Nominal Computation

We recall the nominal modifiers in Lamnso' examined in section 3.2.1. which have to morphologically agree with the noun they modify. We recall also their internal structures with the number class markers. This study claims that after the initial computation, a noun, such as (64) is derived below.

64)	[vi-	bàm]
	Numb	N
	pl.	bag
	'bags'	

(64) is captured by (65):

Given (62(b)), our (65) will seem untenable on conceptual grounds. The argument here is that if vi- and -bàm are computed by operation merge, one of the two must project and (if maximal) be interpreted as a phrase (type) following the stipulation in (62(c)). Our (65) will otherwise not be ruled out, if we substitute our lexical nodes with category tags as in (66) below. (66) unlike (65) does not violate the Endocentricity Principle and the concept of Percolation.

66)

Another 'escape route' for (65) is to exploit the "... not through strict identity" clause of Chomsky (1995) to accept (65) as well-formed. (66) is tenable on 'both the conceptual plane and on the tenets of Lamnso' morphology.

After (64) operation select must choose only an adjective (in case of adjectival modification) that morphologically agrees with the noun as in (67).

53) [vi-_{Adj} bàr]

Pl. red

Operation Merge then computes the two large units within the working area and before spell-out to derive (68) as its output.

68)	[_{NP} yi-	bàm	vi-	129	bár]
	Pl.	bag	pl.		red
	'red bags'				

(68) is compared with other structures that involve the same lexical resources for the formation of an identical NP in (54) and if (54) is judged 'cheapest' and yet converges, it is preferred and chosen.

The entire (68) as an NP is then subjected to the checking theory of the MP.

With (68) in mind, we follow Pollock's (1989) conception of a split-INFL and Chomsky's (1991, 1992) articulated universal clause structure to propose a relational structure within which (68) can have its features checked. This is because the number class marker of the noun and that of the adjective must be identical within the tenets of Lamnso' grammar. We therefore adopt Larson's (1988) VP-internal subject Hypothesis as in (69).

69)

The claim in (69) is that the subject NP is raised from [spec, V'] to [spec-AGR-S"], which is a licensing domain, a position within which the lexical and agreement features of the NP as in (69) are checked. The head of the Lamnso' AGR in (69) will consist of all the number agreement markers for all noun classes in the language; each with the singular/plural distinctions. It is required that any noun that appears in the licensing domain to be checked is assessed on the premise of its appropriate class. The appropriate number marker depends on whether it is in the plural or the singular form. Any of the nominal modifiers is assessed for convergence in the same light.

If (68) is a well-formed NP in Lamnso' (and it is) and satisfies all interface conditions at A-P and C-I (and it does); it converges.

Assume however, that the computation of the same NP, with operation select, for one reason or the other, choosing a different set of lexical items as in (70).

70) *_{NP}[vi- bàm ki- bár]

Numb N Numb Adj

Pl. bag Sing. red

(70) crashes at the interface level, given that there is a lack of number agreement between the noun and its modifier. In other words, in the derivation of (70), operation select fails to take Agreement into account in its choice of number markers presented for merging.

The same analysis will hold for other nominal modifiers in Lamnso'.

3.5.2 The Computation of the INFL component

This section sets out to examine AGR and TNS as functional categories and their operative relations with the subject NP during the computation of the basic clause in Lamnso'.

We recall our postulation of L-features for the subject NP and phi-features for AGR in section 3.3. This study claims that these phi-features are employed to check off the lexical features of the subject NP. AGR in this case is conceived as AGR-S, a head category that stands in a Head-Head relation with the subject NP. Where agreement fails to hold between the two heads, the derivation crashes as in example (70).

Person agreement is captured by (44) (see footnote (14)) by a TNS marker which is the lengthened copy of the final vowel of the subject NP. This final vowel analyzed here as person agreement is distinct from number agreement. Examine the data in (71) to (72):

71) **wu** **u** **tón** **bv̀ə̀y** **bo_la**
 he/she PST roast goat bo_la
 'He/She roasted Bo_la's goat.'

72) **wo** **o** **tón** **bv̀ə̀y** **bo_la**
 you PST roast goat bo_la
 'You roasted Bo_la's goat.'

- 73) *wu o tón bvà̀y bo_la
 he/she PST roast goat bo_la

The subject NPs in (71) and (72) belong to the second and third persons respectively. Their TNS markers are morphologically distinguished accordingly. In (73), the third person TNS marker occurs with the second person subject NP marker. These two constituents lack person agreement as the morphological marker of TNS fails to be determined by the morphological nature of the NP marking person. The clause thus fails to converge.

Following Chomsky (1991, 1992), we can say that in Lamnso', the L-features of the subject NP in [spec, AGR-S"] and the phi-features in AGR-S stand in [spec, Head] agreement relation as shown in example (71) and (72).

On minimalist assumptions, this study postulates TNS movement as shown in (74).

74)

The claim in (74) is that TNS in Lamnso' moves into a checking domain to ensure that its TNS features are checked against the L-features of the subject NP in [spec, AGR-S'']. Notice our claim for right adjunction in (74). AGR-S thus mediates between [spec, AGR-S''] and TNS, which is part of the complex AGR-S head.

3.5.3 The Computation of the VP Component

The internal structure of the Lamnso' verb is as discussed in section 3.4. This study is yet to discover consistent operational relations that exist within the Lamnso' VP. There seems to be no morphological agreement relations between the verb and its NP complement occupying the AGR-O position in the Lamnso' clause. However,

the internal structure of this NP in AGR-O position is identical with that in AGR-S position, given that the two can smoothly interchange position. In such a 'flip-flop' of positions, however, one needs to bear in mind that in accordance with the organization of clausal relations in Lamnso', the INFL and other nominal modifiers, must take their agreement 'cues' from the NP in subject position.

Since the nouns of the language exhibit standard features of a noun class language, it is rather surprising that no morphological agreement relations exist within the Lamnso' VP. Our suggestion here is that, Lamnso' might belong to a subgroup of Bantu languages that Irvine (1937: 56-60) refers to as the "Bantoid". These are languages which, like Lamnso', exhibit a system of class prefixes and a vocabulary reminiscent of Bantu languages but lack verbal morphological characteristics normally ascribed to the Bantu Verbal System. Guthrie (1967: 18-19) describes such languages as "... incomplete Bantu." Such languages, he states, exhibit a verbal system that is frequently complicated, often failing to display even rudiments of their structural features. Such verbs cannot be easily related with fixed rules to a set of hypothetical common roots.

Lamnso' seems to exhibit the characteristics of the so-called "Bantoid" languages described above. This study adopts the Bantoid characteristics as an explanation for the complex and inconsistent internal structure of the Lamnso' verb phrase as discussed in section 3.4. In addition, we suggest that agreement relations with the Lamnso' VP component are abstract in the sense of Chomsky (1991).

3.6 An Articulated Clause Structure for Lamnso'

Following the split-INFL Hypothesis of Pollock (1989), AGR and TNS are now analyzed as functional heads, projecting maximally. However, Chomsky's (1991, 1992) partial universal articulated clause structure in (75) below shows an option of TNS/ASP as functional heads.

75)

The claim in (75) is that we have an option of occurrence of either TNS or ASP. Yuka (1997) claims that (75) does not represent the word order of a simple declarative sentence (in Lamnso), given that TNS and ASP markers do not occur in the same syntactic position in a clause. In addition, the optionality of occurrence of TNS/ASP¹⁸, shown in (75), does not arise in the language. Examine the data below:

- 76) a) **yénla a bóm ø láv**
 yénla PST build ASP+Imp house
 'Yénla was building a house.'
- b) **yénla a bóm ne láv**
 yénla PST build ASP+perf house
 'Yénla had started building a house.'
- c) **yénla a si bóm ø láv**
 yénla PST Incept build ASP+Imp. house
 'Yénla had started building a house.'
- 77) a) **kila ø bóm ø láv**
 kila Non-PST build Asp+Imp house
 'Kila is building a house.'

- b) **kila** $\emptyset$ **bóm** **ne** **láv**
 kila Non-PAST build Asp+Perf. house
 'Kila has built a house.'

- c) **kila** **-ki** **bóm** **ne** **láv**
 kila PST+Immd build ASP + Perf house
 'Kila had (just) built a house.'

Observe from (76) and (77), that like the present tense in Lamnso", the Imperfective (Imp) is not morphologically marked. But unlike the present tense marker which precedes the verbal element, unrealized imperfective, follows the verb and it is signaled by $\emptyset$. Conversely, the Perfective (Perf) is morphologically marked by ne. Notice that unlike in (75) the Aspectual marker for the constructions in (76) and (77) are preceded by the verb. (76) and (77) also show the combination of the Perfective aspect, the Inceptive, and the Immediate Past tenses as examined in Section 3.3.1.

Taking into cognizance that the task of a linguist is to facilitate language learning, it is imperative that all postulated parameter values remain learnable under conditions typically encountered by the language learner. In addition, a language learner will only conceive of those that can be filled by overt constituents, hence the problem of which elements listed in a clause structure are overt or covert is very

important. In other words, the language learner has to discern whether: AGR-S, TNS, V, etc. precede or follow their complements; whether the specifiers of these heads precede or follow their sisters, etc. It is with these questions in mind that Yuka (1997) proposed (78) as an articulated clause structure for Lamnso'.

78)

Given (76) and (77), (78) is well motivated and adequately captures the basic word order in a simple sentence in Lamnso'. ASP as a functional element projects maximally following Hendricks (1991) proposals and Awoyale's (1995) functional categories (for Yoruba).

With more insight, superior argument and on the tenets of constituent order in Lamnso', we find it necessary to revisit (78) as an articulated clause structure for Lamnso' following minimalist interpretation we revise (78) as in (79).

In (79), we demonstrate that the Lamnso' verb undergoes movement to adjoin to the head of ASP" with which it forms a complex head by left adjunction. (79) is more similar in structure to Chomsky's universal articulated clause structure in (75). (79) is tenable on minimalist assumptions, on theoretical conceptions and above all it is capable of accommodating the basic Lamnso' clause.

This study adopts (79) as an articulated clause structure for Lamnso'.

3.7 Summary

In this chapter we have attempted an investigation into the internal structures and the various operative relations that exist within the major components of the basic clause in Lamnso'. The chapter discusses the important issue of computation within the MP and its application on the principal components of the Lamnso' clause. In addition, the chapter proposes an articulated clause structure for Lamnso' following minimalist assumptions.

CHAPTER FOUR

BASIC RELATIONS IN OPERATOR MOVEMENTS IN THE LAMNSO' CLAUSE

4.1 Preliminaries

Given the agreement relations that exist within and between the major components of the basic clause in Lamnso', this chapter sets out to investigate some of the structures that undergo movement in the language, with a view to identifying the specific functions of each 'operator'¹² movement' and the agreement relations which cut across the clause. The chapter seeks to explain the motivation of every move, its extraction site and its landing site. We discuss in addition how movement affects the various agreement relations of a basic clause and argue that every move within the Lamnso' clause is intrinsically agreement governed.

¹²11The term is used in syntax to denote expressions which have the syntactic property of triggering auxilliary inversions. The movement of an operator expression into Spec-CP is referred to as "Operator Movement."

Lamnso' wh-constructions

Radford (1988: 462) proposes a broad division of question type constructions for English: the Yes/No questions, the wh-questions, Echo/Non-echo questions, Direct and Indirect questions. This section takes premise from Radford's analysis of question formation, to examine the structure and properties of wh-constructions in Lamnso'. We confine our discussion to wh-questions because of the peculiarity of their derivation in Lamnso'. In addition, Lamnso' data on wh-question formation seems to provide enough evidence for us to claim that wh-phrases in the language are in-situ in contradistinction to (a large amount of data in) English-type languages which we are exposed to.

The term 'wh-' is generally used in reference to question words that begin with the letters 'wh' in English¹³ (Radford, 1988: 495). For convenience, we will adopt the term 'wh' to make reference to any question formation in Lamnso' which does not necessarily start with the letters 'wh-'. Consider the following Lamnso' sentences in (1):

¹³This requirement is also true of Hausa (cf, Uwalaka, 1992) (cf, Amfani, 1996:330), Igbo and many other African languages.

1) a) lòn e dzə̀v wán ¹⁴⁷ bi'ká
 lòn PST beat child why
 'Why did Lòn beat the child?'

b) yéfon e lé' fó làv bi'ká
 yéfon PST run from house why
 'Why did Yéfon run (away) from home?'

2) a) bvə̀y kila ø beé
 goat kila Non-PST where
 'Where is kila's goat?'

b) kikúm ké tata ki ø' beé
 dress AM tata Numb. Non-PST where
 'Where is Tata's dress?'

3) a) à fíine ø ¹⁴⁸ ηkaa ηgwasan lé
 you sell Non-PST basket corn how
 '(For) how (much) are you selling a basket of corn?'

b) ntasin ø bé' meηká' e kitú lé
 ntasin Non-Past carry firewood on head how
 'How is Ntasin carrying firewood on the head?'

4) a) wán kila a du feé
 child kila PST go where
 'Where did Kila's child go (to)?'

b) kongnyuy wun lukong ø dzà feé
 Kongnyuy and Lukong Non-PST be where
 'Where is Kongnyuy and Lukong?'

- 5) a) kànlá wùn tãrnsa' a koó ká fó kpá' jwim
 kànlá and tãrnsa' PST catch what from bush hunt
 'What did Kànlá and Tãrnsa' catch from the hunt?'

- b) à tá' yi ká
 you wish eat what

'What do you wish to eat?'

- 6) a) wu u tá' du wùn lá e kamarun
 he PST want go with who to cameroon
 'Who did he want to go to Cameroon with?'

- b) lukong e wiy fó bamenda wún lá
 Lukong PST come from Bamenda with who
 'With whom did Lukong return from Bamenda?'

7) a) **vén** **e** **wiy** ¹⁵⁰ **fó** **yún** **kinikí**
 you (pl) PST come to buy which

'Which did you come to buy?'

b) **kila** **wún** **Lòn** **e** **tá'** **yún** **kinikí**
 kila and Lòn PST wish buy which

'Which (one) did Kila and Lòn want to buy?'

Examples (1) to (7) show grammatical question formations in Lamnso' with bi'ká 'why', beé/feé 'where', lé 'how', ká 'what', lá 'who' and kinikí 'which' operate as wh-words. Notice, however that unlike in English-type languages, these wh-words do not move to clause initial position at s-structure. Consider the following s-structure sentences in English and their corresponding D-Structure counterparts in (8 a-b) and (9 a-b) respectively :

8) a) [**Who_i** [**did** _{spec, cp} John see t_i]]
 b) [[**did** _{spec, cp} John see who]]

- 9) a) [What_i]_{cp} [are]_{spec, cp} ¹⁵¹ they playing with t_i]]
- b) []_{cp} [are]_{spec, cp} they playing with what]]

(8a) and (9a) have their wh-phrases moved from clause final position into [spec, cp] at clause initial position. At S-structure level wh-questions are presented in quantificational schemes. Consider (8a) represented in (10) below:

- 10) (which X: X a person) (did John see X)

(10) shows that the transformation of the wh-phrase from its extraction to its landing site provides not only a quantificational schema suitable for interpretation, but also a selectional requirement that binds variables at LF. (see section 4.2.1 for details of such selectional requirements in Lamnso' with their idiosyncrasies).

If our claims about example (1) to (7) are correct, then Lamnso' can be classified among Chinese and Japanese-type languages which do not require the extraction of the wh-phrase to clause initial position at S-structure. We analyse the D-structure and the S-structure wh-constructions in Lamnso', to reveal the nature of the

transformations that generate the surface structure leaving the wh-word in clause-final position. Examine the data below:

11) a) **S-structure**
 [_{cp} $\emptyset$ dzòv_i - $\emptyset$ lá t_j wán]
 Non-PAST beat Asp who child
 'Who is beating the child?'

b) **D-structure**
 [_{cp} [lá_{spec, cp} - $\emptyset$ dzòv - $\emptyset$ wán]]
 who NON-PAST beat Asp. child

12)a) **S-structure**
 [_{cp} $\emptyset$ yí_j $\emptyset$ lá t_j kibán ké wán]
 NON-PAST eat Asp who food of child
 'Who is eating the child's food?'

b) **D-structure**
 [_{cp} [lá_{spec, cp} $\emptyset$ yí $\emptyset$ kibán ké wán]]
 who NON-PAST eat Asp food of child

The verb dzòv "beat" in (11) and yí "eat" in (12) are transitive verbs given that each subcategorises for an object NP as follows:

13) a) dzòv, [____ NP]

b) yí, [____ NP]

In the transformation from (11a) to (11b) and (12a) to (12b) we would traditionally expect lá "who" to move leftwards. Such a movement is not possible in (11) and (12) understandably because lá will be moving out of an A-position. To move rightwards, it must move into another A-position, but such a position is already occupied by the object NP wán 'child'. Again the movement of lá into [spec, cp] will not effect any change in the syntactic arrangement of the constituents in the string. In addition (11b) as a derivation is not legitimate in Lamnso' and thus fails to converge. We therefore propose V-movement which saves (11b) from crashing as shown in its S-structure in (11a).

Notice however that the verb dzòv will have to move into the head of I', to have tense features associated with it, before it finally moves into its landing site as represented in (14 a-b) below.

14)a) D-Structure

b) S-Structure

(14) above shows that the verb dzòv does not move into the head of CP (its landing site) in 'one fell swoop' (Uriagereka, 1988). It obeys the MP economy Principle of Shortest Move, by moving first into the head of IP (a potential landing site) that constitutes the first position of the right kind, up from the source position. The complex head of I eventually moves into the head of CP, yielding a well formed structure in Lamnso'. Notice that the derivation in (14b) yields a structure with the initial constituent being TNS. We recall from Chapter Three that tense in Lamnso' is morphologically dependent on the subject NP. In like manner, the language does not morphologically mark present tense. If the derivation in (14b) were to be realised in the past tense, the language will simply base generate a pleonastic element in subject NP position (yii, 'it') on which the past tense will be morphologically dependent as discussed in section 3.3.

4.2.1 Lamnso' as a wh-in-situ Language

The meeting point of a language like Lamnso' in which wh-words are not moved at S-structure and English-type languages in which wh-words obligatorily move to clause initial position at S-structure is the LF. Languages are not distinguished

principally on whether they have wh-movement or not since all languages have wh-movement at the instance of the rule $\text{move } -\alpha \text{ at LF}$. The difference lies rather in whether wh-movement is syntactically overt or not. Lamnso' does not seem to exhibit syntactic wh-movement. We examine its peculiar characteristics immediately.

Cheng (1991) claims that an idiosyncrasy of languages like Lamnso' is that routinely, they exhibit a question particle at clause final position, as against English-type languages that lack such question particles. For instance, in Chinese, Yes/No questions require the final particle ma, while wh-questions and disjunctive questions optionally take the particles ne. ka or no is required for all Japanese questions.

Consider the following data (Cf Marantz, 1995: 36).

- 15) a) ni Xiang mai shenme (ne)?
 you want buy what Q

'What do you want to buy?'

- b) ni Xiang mai shenme ma?
 you want buy something Q

'Would you like to buy something?'

In like manner, the final question particle **á** is required for all Lamnso' questions which do not exhibit a wh-word in its construction. For example:

16) a) **yénla wun kila a du yaounde á**
 yénla and Kila PST go yaounde Q

'Did Yénla and Kila go to Yaounde?'

b) **yii i dù yénla wun lá yaounde**
 it PST go yénla and who yaounde

'Who did Yénla go with to Yaounde?'

17) a) **audu u kóy yí nyám fó ntòn á**
 audu PST want eat meat from pot Q

'Did Audu want to eat meat from the pot?'

- b) **audu u kóy yí nyám fó ghá**
 audu PST want eat meat from what
'What did Audu want to eat meat from?'

Notice from (16a) and (17a) that the clauses are intrinsically wh-constructions. The question formation is indicated by the final question particle **á**. Sentences (16b) and (17b) present the same constructions, but with the question formation captured by the wh-word. Notice that **lá** and **ká** encode both the prepositional object **kila** and the question particle (for 16a). Our explanation of this phenomenon is that the question particle is always suggestive of the answer to the question. Our claim in (16) to (17) is that languages such as Lamnso' have a variation strategy in question formation, by simply base generating a question particle at clause final position.

The general assumption is that interrogative wh-phrases comprise two cardinal components. There is the presupposition of the question and there is the object of 'focus'¹⁴ of that question, as shown in examples (18) below:

¹⁴"focus" here is not used in the technical sense.

18)	<u>lá</u>	implies	wh-	+	160	someone
	<u>ká</u>	implies	wh-	+		something
	<u>feé</u>	implies	wh-	+		a place, etc.

From (18) one can, by extension, claim that each wh-word has features associated with it that make it a question word. Such features represent the object for which clarification is being sought. Put differently, wh-phrases are tagged "existential quantifiers" because apart from accounting for question selection, they as well fix the scope of the wh-phrase as a quantifier.

The wh-word is therefore associated with the features in (19) that identify the constituent in question.

19)	wh-word								
	<table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">±</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">concrete</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">±</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">count</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">±</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">human</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;">±</td> <td style="padding: 5px;">sing</td> </tr> </table>	±	concrete	±	count	±	human	±	sing
±	concrete								
±	count								
±	human								
±	sing								

Thus in (16b), the speaker presupposes that someone went with Yénla to Yaounde; the question demands for specification of who it is that Yénla went to Yaounde with. A clue to the expected answer is found in the features of the wh-word lá, 'who' which are as in (20).

20) lá

+	N
+	count
+	human
+	sing .

The features in (20) are identical to and neatly fit with those of the NP which is the appropriate answer to lá. Put differently, Lamnso' grammar requires that the object NP in (21) which is the answer to (16b) should bear identical features with lá in (20).

21) yénla a du wún kila¹⁶²

yénla PST go with kila

'Yénla went with Kila.'

Thus the wh-in-situ phrase in Lamnso' must be in the domain of some appropriate binder at L.F., for the phrase to be interpreted as an interrogative phrase. Examine the constructions below:

22) m ø tá' yún kifa.

i Non-PST want buy something

'I want to buy something.'

23) à ø tá' yún kifa á.

you Non-PST want buy something Q

'Do you want to buy something?'

24) à ø tá' yún ká.
 you Non-PST want buy what

'What do you want to buy?'

Observe that in (22) through (24), tá' 'want' and yún 'buy' are transitive verbs that subcategorise for object NPs. In (24) yún has the wh-word as its object NP, while tá' lacks an overt object NP. Underlyingly, the NP for tá' and yún are identical in ká. Thus the correct interpretation of the wh-word in (24) is dependent on the correct interpretation of the wh-word as a quantifier. Therefore, the in-situ wh-phrases in Lamnso' must always be bound by another NP at LF with identical features to those of the wh-word.

Wh- elements only undergo movement when translated as 'cleft' eg

dzà la_i wó kila a yuirin
 be who that kila TNS kill

In all other constructions involving wh- elements, such are in-situ.

English-type languages, like Lamnso' also have wh-movement at LF. In English, an object wh-in-situ is allowed but not a subject in-situ for example:

- 25) a) $[_{cp} \text{who}_i \quad [_{spec, cp} t_i \text{ killed }^{164} \text{ [what]?' }]]$
- b) $[_{cp} \text{what}_i \text{ did } [_{cp} \text{ who killed } t_i]]$

(25 a-b) show that English prohibits more than one wh-phrase from overtly moving into [SPEC,CP]. Taking cognisance of the Superiority Condition discussed in section 3.3.2, movement of the second wh-phrase what must wait to move only at LF as required by the MP principle of procrastinate.

In Lamnso' multiple wh-clauses have their wh-phrases occurring consecutively in the syntactic string at S-structure. Examine example (26):

- 26) a) $[_{cp} [_{spec, cp} \text{yii} \text{ -[ii yuiri]}_j \text{ lá } t_i \text{ } t_i \text{ k } \text{ á}]]$
- b) $[_{cp} [_{spec, cp} \text{lá } \text{ a } \text{ yuiri } \text{ ká }]]$

In (26a) the verb and its associated features move into TNS, to pick up the appropriate TNS features. This movement forms a complex head TNS which then moves into the checking domain, its landing site. By landing in the TNS position as

the "provisional landing site" (26a) obeys the economy principle of shortest move. Notice the positions of the wh-words in (26).

4.3 Relative Constructions in Lamnso'

Relative clauses have been given quite some attention in the literature; (Williams (1996), Huang (1995), Reimsdijk and Williams (1986) Keenan and Comrie (1979) and other works. Reimsdijk and Williams (1986: 93) have outlined the various properties of relative clauses with the wh-phrases at S-structure, retaining the following characteristics for English.

- 27)
- a) there is always a wh-word on the surface structure in Composition,
 - b) the construction has a gap in S, dominated by S'
 - c) the gap and the wh-word are governed by subjacency
 - d) there is preposition stranding
 - e) only NPs and PPs can be moved
 - f) the gap left by the wh-word blocks construction

- h) the head of NP is related to the gap

The rather detailed characteristics of relativised clauses in (27 a-h) involve a number of assumptions that require further analysis. We are motivated for such an analysis by the preconception that an examination of relative clause constructions in Lamnso' will reveal intricate operational relations within constituents of the Lamnso' clause. Examine the English data in (28) to (31).

28) Peter killed a dog.

29) The dog Peter killed.

According to Keenan and Comrie (1979), the relativisation of (28) and (29) necessitates that we identify all the NPs in the clauses. Among these NPs is the Head NP which may or may not be a syntactic head of the construction. Then we single out the restricting clause and relativise its direct object. If we apply these strategies of relativisation to (28) through (29), (30) through (31) will be our output.

30) [[Peter] [who_i t_i killed a dog]]

31) [[The dog] that_i Peter killed t_i]

We examine relative constructions in Lamnso' with a view to determining the morphological features of the relative marker and the syntactic distribution of

constituents in the language. Consider the following data which show the S-structure and Deep structure of each construction respectively.

32) a) **[kila_{cp} [wól t_iwu u duún e bamenda]]**

kila AM he PST go+ to bamenda
Rel.

'Kila who went to Bamenda.'

b) **[kila] [Kila_{cp} a du e bamenda]**

kila kila PST go to bamenda

33) a) **[gáy [wó_i t_i wu u yuirin]]**

Shepherd AM he PST kill+Rel goat

'The Shepherd who killed the goat.'

b) **[agáy [vé_i t_i ve e yuirin bvày]]**

Shepherds AM they PST kill+Rel. goat

'The Shepherds who killed the goat.'

c) [gáy],_{NP} [gáy]_{NP} e yuiri bvə̀y]
 Shepherd Shepherd PST kill goat

34) a) [shinə̀n [shé_{cp} t_i shi -ii yíin sáŋ]]
 bird AM it PST eat+Rel rice
 'The bird which ate the rice.'

b) [menə̀n [mé_{cp} t_i me e yíin sáŋ]]
 birds AM they PST eat+Rel rice
 'The birds which ate the rice.'

c) [shinə̀n]_{NP} [shinə̀n]_{NP} shi i yí sáŋ]
 bird bird AM PST eat rice

35) a) [kitàm [ké_{cp} t_i ki i bá'an kici]]
 elephant AM it PST fell+Rel tree
 'The elephant that felled the tree.'

b) [vità_{CP}m [vé_i t_i¹⁶⁹ vi i bá'an kicī]]
 elephants AM they PST fell tree
 'The elephants which felled the tree.'

c) [kítà_{NP}m] [kítà_{NP}m ki i bá' kicī]
 elephant elephant it PST fell tree

36) a) [ngà_{CP}v [ye_i t_i yi i má'an wúm]]
 fowl AM it PST lay+Rel egg
 'The fowl that laid eggs.'

b) [ngà_{CP}vsi [se_i t_i si i má'an wúm]]
 fowls AM they PST lay+Rel eggs
 'The fowls which laid eggs.'

c) [ngà_{NP}v][ngà_{NP}v e má' wúm]
 fowls fowls PST lay eggs

In (32a) which is the relativised form of (32b), the pronominal AM marker wó occurs between the head of the construction kila and wu 'he', the subject of the

restricting clause. The AM marker in (32a) surfaces as wó given that kila like all names in Lamnso' fall under class 1 nouns. In (33b), this AM marker for class 1 nouns, surfaces as vé since the head noun of the construction is a class 1 plural noun (see section 3.2.1.2 for details). Thus vé occurs in agreement with number, since vé is the plural form of wó. As a relativisation strategy for Lamnso', wó undergoes vacuous movement into the head of the clause.

Relativisation (of the subject) in Lamnso' therefore requires two obligatory NPs, (the subject at the Head of the construction and the subject of the restricting clause). It is the subject of the restricting clause that is converted into an AM. This AM comprises of a number marker and an associative marker. The morphological realization of the AM is dependent on the head noun of the construction with which it shares identical features.

(32) to (36) reveal that the verbs take a relative clause extension, each time there is an element occupying the head CP of the clause. Examine the verbs in (37) drawn from the data presented in examples (32) to (36).

36) a) yí -----> 171
yi + ín
'eat' 'eat+Rel'

b) du -----> du + ún
'go' 'go+Rel'

c) té -----> te + én
'shoot' 'shoot+Rel'

d) yuiri -----> yuiri + ín
'kill' 'kill+Rel'

e) bá' -----> ba' + án
'fell' 'fell+Rel'

English, variously as it, they, etc. . In addition, these number agreement markers determine the morphological nature of TNS. We return to a detailed analysis of their relationship with the matrix noun in section 4.6.1 of this chapter.

In view of the following observations, we can now consider relativised clauses with wh-NPs in Lamnso'. Examine the following examples:

- 38) a) **yii i dzə́ ká [ké_{cp} kila a yuirin t_i]**
 it PST is what AM kila PST kill+Rel

'What was it that Kila killed?'

- b) ***yii i dzə́ [ká_{NP} kila a yuiri ká]**
 It PST is what kila PST kill what

- 39)a) **yii i dzə́ lá [wó_{cp} kici ki i lémirin t_i]**
 it PST is who AM tree it PST wound+Rel

'Who was it that the tree wounded?'

b) *yi i dzə́ lá ¹⁷⁴ [kici_{NP} kii i lémer á]
 It PST is who tree it PST wound who

The object NPs in the restricting clauses above are lá and ká, which are wh-NPs in Lamnso'. In such constructions, these object NPs move into the head of CP position with relativisation being the motivation of movement. At their landing sites, they surface as pronominal AM markers (AM cum Relative pronoun). We proceed to state here that these wh-NPs are not motivated by question transformation to move. In addition they move as relative pronouns and are thus coindexed with the AM marker. Evidence to wh-in-situ in Lamnso' still stands given that the wh-elements in the matrix clause of the same constructions appear in clause final position.

4.4 The Movement of NP Structures in Lamnso'

Following the standard assumption of the structure of an NP, the obligatory element within the NP is the head noun identified as [+N - V] (Chomsky, 1981). In Lamnso', this head noun bears the distinctive features of its class. All other constituents that modify this head noun are satellites (Sells, 1985) with structural

agreement features identical to the head noun. In our analysis of the movement of NP structures in Lamnso', we will consider the head noun, and its various satellites as a single entity. Radford's (1988) concept of NP-movement is that of a rule, that moves an NP into a matching empty NP slot. Put differently, NP-movement is viewed as a substitution rule. In agreement with such an analysis, Riemsdijk and Williams (1986) claim that NP-movement involves two operations NP-Pre-posing and NP-post-posing.

We proceed to examine movement structures in Lamnso' that yield Passive, Raising and Focused structures. Such an investigation (it is expected) will enable us determine the various motivations for NP-movement in the language, the characteristics of their extraction and landing sites and how such movements affect the agreement relations within the Lamnso' clause.

4.5 Ergative Constructions in Lamnso'

Standardly, ergative constructions are said to be those with no overt NP in subject position at D-structure. The clause object NP is not case-marked, a syntactic condition that provides a motivation for it to move into a position at which it can be

assigned case. NP-movement in passive constructions is a typical instance of A-movement (Lasnik and Uriagereka 1992: 20). Consider the following sentences:

40) a) **lòn_i e lúmír t_i méndzə̀v**

lòn PST warm+causative water

'Lòn warmed the water.'

b) **méndzə̀v me e lúm.**

water Numb PST warm

'The water warmed.'

41) a) **kila_i a màysi ti kún wán**

kila PST finish + completive beans child

'Kila finished the child's beans.'

b) **kún wán e mày**

beans child PST finish

'The child's beans finished.'

Notice the difference between the ergative and the active constructions in (40) and (41) above. The active constructions show the overt movement of the subject NP's Lòn and Kila from their post-verbal position to clause initial position. These NPs are triggered to move by the quest to have their lexical features checked. This checking is done within the licensing domain of the NP by the head of AGR"-S as shown in (42).

42)

Notice that the passive verbal forms in (40b) and (41b) lack the verbal extensions of their active counterparts. The traces reveal an identity of thematic functions between the S-structure and the D-structure. Where a lexical item fills the extraction site of the moved NP, the derivation crashes as in (43).

In (43b) the subject NP, kún wán does not originate from the immediate right of the "natural predicate" (Riemsdijk and Williams, 1986). In addition, no NP extraction is permitted across another NP in passive constructions. Ergative constructions are therefore subject to Proximity Conditions which require that only an NP, structurally next to the immediate right of yí in (43) is visible to move $-\alpha$. In (43a), Lòn which occurs to the immediate right of yí does not move as expected because the subject NP position which is the expected landing site is already filled by kila, and thus blocks movement. Thus Lòn which is phonetically realised lacks identity of reference with kila in the subject position, thus rendering the derivation illegitimate.

Raising Structures in Lamnso'

Raising structures involve the movement of an S complement away from the subject position of an embedded clause into the matrix clause where it becomes the superficial subject of the main clause (Radford, 1988). NP-movement in raising structures is another instance of A-movement. Wekker and Haegeman (1982) claim that such structures can be achieved with passive verbs, intransitive verbs and adjectives. Though not identical, raising structures are very similar to passive constructions. Examine the following sentences:

44) [kila_s a ki' [mu t_s wu u lémir kitúkʃə]]

Kila PST appear as he PST wound head
+causative +his

'Kila appears to have wounded himself.'

45) [ntá'_s a ki' [mu t_s wu u shwí e lāv]]

chair PST appear to it PST burn in house

'The chair appears to (have) been burnt in the house.'

46) [bvə̀ysi_j i yénsin [mu t_s si i dzà si júŋ]]
 goats PST seem as Numb PST is Numb good
 'The goats seemed to (have) been good.'

47) [kibám_j ki i yénsin [mu t_s ki i dzà kisán]]
 bag Numb PST seem to Numb PST is empty
 'The bag seem to (have) been empty.'

48) [ʃhinə̀n_j shi i yénsin [mu t_s shi i dzà shimó'òn]] _
 bird Numb PST seem to Numb PST is one
 'The bird seemed to (have) been one.'

We recall that all names in Lamnso' fall under class 1 nouns within the Lamnso' noun class system. Example (44) shows that wu 'he/she' is a pleonastic element in the subject position of the embedded clause, once the substantive subject NP kila is driven by morphological necessity to the matrix subject position where it is licensed. Notice however that for classes 3 and 4 nouns in example (47) to (48) respectively,

it is their number agreement markers that surface to the right of the trace of the moved NP. This analysis is also true for class 2 nouns as shown in example (46). These number markers determine the morphological nature of TNS in these structures just as wu does for (44) and (45). The number class marker must of necessity have identical features with the noun and its associate modifiers.

We are rather hesitant to refer to these number class marker in the embedded clause as a resumptive pronoun given that the noun and this number class markers can co-exist in derivations that converge in the language. (see section 4.4.2.1 for details). However, our claims regarding example (46) to (48) are that it is the noun in the NP position of the embedded clause and its prefix marker that trigger the chain of agreement relations that run through the entire clause. Observe the data in (49) and (50):

49)*[kibà_i ki i yénsin[mu t_i wu u dzà kisan]]

bag Numb PST seem as he/she PST is empty

50)*[Kila_i a ki' [mu t_i ki i lémir kitúkfà]

Kila PST appear as Numb PST wound head+his

In (49) and (50) there is no agreement of features between the wu, ki and kibàm, kila respectively. As a consequence, the L-features of wu and ki are uninterpretable and fail to be eliminated before spell-out. In addition notice that each time we have the verb yénsin or ki' the CP complement must take the infinitival element mu. It is mu that motivates the raising of the NP. The suggestion here is that yénsin and ki' are raising verbs in the language. In Lamnso' therefore, we can say that mu is the infinitival marker and the Lamnso' strategy for NP raising.

4.6.1 Towards PRO-Drop in Lamnso'

Italian, Japanese and Chinese -type languages have been shown to exhibit the null subject parameter. These are languages that can have a missing subject in clauses. They have variously been described as Pro-drop, subject drop or simply null-subject languages. Chomsky (1981: 240) enumerates "clustering properties" related to the Pro-drop parameter. Consider the following example of Pro-drop in Denya¹⁵ * (Abangma, 1991: 167-168).

¹⁵ A language spoken in Momo Division in the North West Province of Cameroon.

51) a) **eva a- wá** ¹⁸⁴ **meshu njuú.**
 eva AGR kill(perf) elephant yesterday
 'Eva killed an elephant yesterday'

b) **ji a- wá** **meshu njuú.**
 him AGR kill (perf) elephant yesterday
 'He killed an elephant yesterday.'

c) **Pro ø- wá** **meshu njuú.**
 kill (perf) elephant yesterday
 'He killed an elephant yesterday.'

In (51c) there is the empty pronominal (pro) which is recovered by Denya's 'rich' inflectional morphology given the verb/subject agreement.

We take premise from the concept of null-subject parameter to suggest the existence of a Pro-drop phenomenon in Lamnso', though the phenomena does not

55) kikú ké téri ki i¹⁸⁶ shwí e láv.
 bed AM small Numb PST burn in house

'The small bed was burnt in the house.'

(52) - (55) show that the number agreement marker follows the adjectival modifier of the noun. The adjectival marker unlike other nominal modifiers, does not take a number agreement marker of the noun it modifies. We argue that it is because of the intervention of the AM, that the adjectival modifier does not take its number agreement marker. One could even go further to claim that it is this adjectival agreement marker that noun surfaces after the adjective. But then, fundamentally adjectives do not take suffixes in their own right, they only do so when modifying a noun and in such instances it is the nominal prefix of the noun that they take. We therefore argue that it is the noun in the matrix subject position that is underlyingly repeated after the adjectival modifier but is deleted at surface level, leaving behind the number agreement marker as a ghost copy of itself. (It's this ghost copy, that we were tempted to refer to in section 4.4.2 as the resumptive pronoun). Evidence of such a claim is that the prefix of the noun in subject position

and the number agreement marker that determines the morphological nature of tense are identical both morphologically and in features. This means that the two prefixes precede the same noun. In other words, the matrix noun is represented by its prefix marker. To task our analysis further, we conceive of this derivation as an equivalent of the Pro-drop parameter where a noun is dropped but yet its features can be discerned or interpreted from another constituent in the construction. (We can determine both the noun class and the features of the missing noun from its prefix marker). Lamnso', then, like Pro-drop languages must have a mechanism of recovering the missing information about the covert NP. Yuka (1997) has shown that Lamnso' does not exhibit a 'rich' enough inflectional morphology given the verb-object morphological relationship. However, there exist ample evidence of subject-INFL agreement relations. Our suggestion is that on account of this subject-INFL agreement, the morphological conditions that prevent the missing noun from being overtly represented in the clauses in example (52) to (55) are not unconnected with the fact that within the Lamnso' noun class system, it is the head noun (in subject position) that triggers the chain of intricate agreement relations that run through the clause. In conformity with the economy of derivations of the MP, Lamnso' seems to

choose not to (overtly) represent those constituents that can be interpreted within a given configuration. This is our explanation for the lone appearance of the nominal number agreement marker that surfaces after the adjective in example (53) to (55) without the noun.

4.7 Cleft Constructions in Lamnso'

Riemsdijk and Williams (1986) and Radford (1988) refer to movement processes in which communicative emphasis is laid on a given constituent within the clause, over and above the surrounding constituent as Topicalisation (cf. Ndemeli, 1992). Teke (1987: 7) unifies all leftward movements as instances of topicalisation. He postulates the rule in (56):

56) Move α into Top.

We leave (56) and its overgeneralised concepts that generate complicated arguments and simply examine any movement whose motivation for movement is to lay communicative emphasis on the moved constituent over and above other constituents in a clause, as an instance of cleft construction.

Like Raising constructions, focus derivations is another type of $_$ -movement. Following Chomsky's (1986) rejection of his (1977: 84) claim that such movement lands in comp rather than in the [spec, cp]. Chomsky (1986: 3) states the following rules:

57) a) $S = I' = [NP V...]$

b) $S' = C' = [C...[C'I']]$

Notice that in (57a) CP is not within the minimal sentence, movement is then into [spec, cp] which must be outside S. In (57b) movement will be into comp which is within the minimal sentence. We follow (57) in our analysis of focus constructions in Lamnso'. We have chosen to present examples from a cross-section of some elements that can be focused in the language (in a stretch simply to avoid repetition, given the identity of most issues that run across the data). We however attempt to isolate the issues unique to particular focused elements for discussion. Examine the following constructions:

58) a) kila a yuir¹⁹⁰ ká.

kila PST kill what

'What did Kila kill?'

b) yii i dzà ka_i ké kila a yuirin t_i.

It PST is(foc)what AM kila PST kill+Rel.

'What was it (that) kila killed?'

59) a) lòn e shón mbàm.

lòn PST steal money

'Lòn stole money.'

b) yi i dzà mbàm sé Lòn e shónin t_i.

it PST is(foc) moneyAM Lò PST steal+Rel

'It was money that Lòn stole.'

60) a) kila wùn Lò e dzà mvam lāv.

kila and Lò PST is inside house

'Kila and Lò were inside the house.'

b) **yii** **i** **dzə̀**¹⁹¹ **kila** **wùn** **Lòn** **t** **mvəm láv.**
 it PST is(foc) Kila and Lòn inside house
 'It was Kila and Lòn inside the house.'

61) a) **mu** **u** **yí** **ré'** **kila.**
 j PST eat yam kila
 'I ate Kila's yam'

b) **yii** **i** **yí** **mu** **ti** **ré'** **Kila.**
 it PST eat I yam Kila
 '(What I did) was eat Kila's yam.'

(58) to (61) are cleft constructions in Lamnso' which show the movement of focused constituents from an A-position to an _-position of the clause. Notice from (58a), (59a) through (61a) that the elements that undergo movement are extracted from positions within which their features have been duly checked. This is why such constructions are grammatical in the language. These elements still undergo

movement, motivated by the quest to lay communicative emphasis on such moving constituents.

Observe that the cleft constructions in (58) to (61) are morphologically marked by the presence of yii in clause initial position. We are tempted to analyse yii as the focus marker in the language. Notice also that it is yii that morphologically determines tense, which in all cases is in the past. What then happens if we have constructions of focused elements in the present tense. Consider the constructions in (62):

62) a) **kila** $\emptyset$ **yui** **ká.**
 kila Non-PST kill what

'What is Kila killing?'

b) **dzə** **ka** **ké** **Kila** **yui** **t.**
 is what AM Kila kill

'What is it (that) Kila is killing?'

Notice from (62) that ká 'what' is focused even in the absence of yii. Though yii features in all focus constructions in examples (58) - (61). We cannot claim then that it is the focus marker in the language. Our earlier analysis of yii as a pleonastic element is maintained.

Our claim then is that dzò is the focus marker in the language. Focused elements standardly require a morphologically overt focus marker which normally precedes the element being focused. The focus marker in Lamnso' exhibits verbal features and thus is itself preceded by TNS (we return to this shortly).

Focused elements in Lamnso' also require an associative marker which relates the subject NP of the matrix clause to that of the embedded clause. Such an AM agrees in features with the focused elements (see section 3.2.1.2 for a detailed discussion of the AM).

Notice from (62 a-b) that focused elements do not have an AM marker because such constructions do not exhibit two nominal elements nor any adjectival qualities that need to be related. In addition, because the focus marker belongs to the category [-N, +V], focused VP-elements do not overtly have the focus marker as shown in example (61 a-b). If the focus marker were overt in such constructions, we

will have a derivation with two consecutive verbal elements to account for. Such constructions are rather distant from the phenomenon of consecutivization which readily comes to mind.

Examples (58) through (61) show that it is the nominal element in the subject position of the clause that triggers the chain of agreement relations within the Lamnso' clause. The subject NP of the embedded clause plays this role once it is focused.

4.8 V-Movement in Lamnso'

In his analysis of verbal inflections, Chomsky (1965) adopts Affix-Hopping (flip-flop) rule as a standard rule to account for the relationship between the Aux (auxiliary) and the verbal element sketched in (62).

$$63) \quad \text{Aff} + \text{V} \Rightarrow \text{V} + \text{Aff}$$

(62) states that every affix (Aff) that is immediately followed by a verb must be attached on the verb, i.e., the affix and the verb flip-flop or exchange positions.

Working within the P & P framework, Koopman (1984) and Tellier (1987) establish that Kru languages such as "Vata" and Western Kwa languages such as 'Abe' show that verbs are moved from their natural sites to positions within which they are inflected. Chomsky (1986) and Radford (1988) are agreed that in English, finite clauses, where I is empty have their verbs moved into the empty I (head of INFL) by a V-movement rule. V-movement like NP-movement in Ergative structures is a 'local process' in which the head V moves into an empty slot of another head category. It is a good example of Head-to-Head movement. Unlike the NP-movement which requires the movement of the entire maximal projections, V-movement necessitates only the movement of the head of VP.

Unlike in English-type languages where an element in I blocks V-movement, Lamnso' verbs become inflected by the element in I through right adjunction.

Examine the following derivations:

64) a) **kila a yuiri bv̄ɔy**

kila PST kill goat

'Kila killed a goat.'

65)

a)

b)

Notice from (64b) that yii, the pleonastic element is base-generated in [spec, AGR-S"] position.

Another instance of V-movement in Lamnso' is exhibited in our conception of the articulated clause structure for Lamnso' examined in section 3.6. In our claim of V-movement in example (63) of Chapter Three, we postulated that the head V moves and adjoins the head of ASP forming a complex ASP phrase through left adjunction. The motivation is orchestrated by the need to have aspectual features inflected onto the Verb. Ultimate V-movement in Lamnso' is an 'escape route' that enables us to further parameterize Chomsky's (1991, 1992) articulated universal clause structure. This is due to the idiosyncrasy of Lamnso' clauses whose aspectual marker follows the verb as shown in (65):

66) **audu u yúrine bvà̃y.**

Audu PST kill+Asp goat

'Audu had killed the goat.'

We represent V-movement within the Lamnso' Partial articulated clause structure which accommodates (66) above in (67).

V-movement in (66) is self-serving. It moves to satisfy its want of aspectual features which it gets through left-adjunction to the head of the ASP''.

Summary

This chapter set out to investigate some of the elements that undergo movement in the Lamnso' clause. Our interest in such structures was to determine how such movements affect the established operational relations that exist between the major constituents of the Lamnso' clause. We have examined wh-constructions in the language which reveal that Lamnso' is a wh-in-situ language. Relative constructions have been given a closer look. The chapter exploits the features of wh-words as existential quantifiers to claim that in Relative constructions in Lamnso' it is the subject NP that triggers the agreement relations that run through the clause. The chapter concludes that given our example (16) to (17), Lamnso' has a variation strategy in question formation, by base generating a question particle at clause final position, the general assumption being that interrogative wh-phrases comprise two cardinal components. Apart from the peculiarities of focus constructions, the chapter has also discussed V-movement. V-movement within the Lamnso' articulated clause structure has led us to further parameterize Chomsky's (1991, 1992) articulated universal clause structure to enable it accommodate the Lamnso' clausal constituent order.

CHAPTER FIVE

THE ECONOMY PRINCIPLES AND THE LAMNSO' CLAUSE

5.1 Preliminaries

The economy principles²⁶ of the MP are designed to constrain an overgenerating syntax. In addition, they compare and choose derivations that are more nearly optimal than others. Chapter three of this study examines the computation of the major constituents that are syntactically ordered to derive the Lamnso' clause. This chapter sets out to evaluate the adequacy of these principles vis-à-vis Lamnso' grammar. In the light of the idiosyncrasies of the language, the chapter proposes amendments to these principles to ensure that they accommodate data from Lamnso' and Lamnso'-type languages. Other conceptions of the MP are also given a closer look.

²⁶ Some of the infinite number of principles consistent with the general economy considerations Chomsky (1995) emphasizes that the strict forms these principles take in constraining syntax cannot follow from the general extralinguistic notions of 'economy'. Economy in the sense of Chomsky (1995) refers to the

Within the PP framework, each time the rule $\text{move } -\alpha$ is applied, α is moved from its extraction site (X) to a landing site (Y) leaving behind a trace at X. X and Y are linked by a chain with Y as the head of the chain and X its tail. An additional logical assumption is that any thematic role associated with X is associated with Y as well. However, the material in X, it is further assumed, gets deleted at PF and is thus not pronounced. Only the head of the chain is phonetically realized at PF. (see the organization of grammar within the standard GB framework in example (26) of chapter two).

The MP adopts the standard concepts of the copy theory of movement. It differs however in its specification of the motivation for every constituent that undergoes movement. The MP stipulates that every constituent moves only to check its own morphological features. It discourages any movement that is altruistic or not self-serving. This study argues that the copy theory of movement adopted by the MP from the PP is weak because only the head of the chain ends up in the checking domain. The tail of the chain, represented by the trace contains unchecked

requirement that (all other things being equal) syntactic representations should

morphological features since it doesn't occur within the licensing domain. These unchecked features should expectedly cause the assumed well-formed derivation within the MP to crash. But they don't.

Chomsky (1992) attempts to remedy the MP's movement theory from the identified defect with his proposition of the 'deletion solution'. His suggestion is that all material at the tail of the chain be deleted before the interface levels while maintaining the material at the head of the chain.

We argue against the deletion solution of Chomsky (1992) in support of the original conception of chains meant to ensure recoverability of the pre-movement structure of the clause. Instead of 'deletion' we borrow the ideas of the PP framework to propose that on theoretical conceptions, the checking of the head chain be interpreted as the checking of the entire chain. This suggestion ensures that there are no unchecked features within a clause that converges and that the pre-movement clause structure can be fully recovered without losing any constituent. Therefore the checking of the features of the Head NP in example (8) of chapter two, repeated here as example (1) are interpreted as the checking of the features of the trace of the NP that has undergone movement.

contain few constituents and involve as few grammatical operations as possible.

1)

a) **kila_j a yuiri t_j²⁰⁵ bv̀əy**
kila PST kill goat

'Kila killed a goat.'

(1a) is schematically captured by (1b).

1) b)

Distance of Movement Issues

5.2.1

Shortest move as a metric towards the economy of derivations states that, a constituent must move to the first position of its kind from its source position. In other words the position that is hierarchically closest from its extraction site. For instance, in example (5) of chapter one, repeated in (2) below, the verb is not permitted to move directly into AGR-S in 'one fell swoop' skipping over head TNS; it must move to TNS before proceeding to AGR-S occasioning a Head to Head movement.

2)

'Eating yam is what Kila is doing'

Notice from (2) above that the initial V-movement into TNS leaves the V-features of the verb unchecked since the position of the complex head of TNS'' is not a checking domain. Our claim is that such a move fails to respect the feature checking as a motivation for movement as stipulated by the MP, though the MP tends to

exploit the quest for the moving head verb to be associated with TNS features to explain this movement. Given the unchecked features of the verb within the complex head of TNS", the derivation will crash at the interface levels. The MP also fails to specify whether the illegitimate derivation results from the unchecked V-features or from altruistic move of the verb. We return to this shortly.

Another argument that we proffer for nominal movement is why for instance, does an NP move from its natural site (eg, the specifier of V) to AGR-S, instead of to AGR-O, which is closest to its source as stipulated by the principle of shortest move, "... a constituent must move to the first position which is hierarchically closest to its extraction site". Examine (3) below:

3)

Observe from (3) that between the two possible landing sites of the NP in [spec, V⁰], (AGR-S and AGR-O) only AGR-S is equipped with a licensing domain with the right kind of features that can check a subject NP. Considering the subject NP-INFL agreement relation in Lamnso', it is only AGR-S that can ensure the right kind of number agreement and the agreement of the L-features and the phi-features of the Lamnso' subject NP and the head of AGR-S respectively. The movement in (3) is more appropriate within the Lamnso' grammar because the language does not overtly exhibit morphological agreement relations between the verb and the object NP in AGR-O, thus if such morphological features must be checked to ensure convergence the appropriate checking domain is AGR-S. Other languages will therefore have to take the peculiarities of agreement relations into consideration before choosing the appropriate landing site for the NP in (spec, V⁰). Hausa, for instance, with its rich verbal grade, will need to specify not only the features of the subject NP but those of the object NP as well, given that the verbal component in Hausa comprises of the verbal base, AGR-O and its syntactic environment (Amfani 1995: 132). The agreement relations that exist within the Hausa verbal component is

ensured by AGR-O, which is not the case with Lamnso'. Consider the Hausa data below.

What the discussion above emphasizes is that shortest move as an MP economy metric cannot be said to be a universal filter as claimed within the MP. The suggestion of this study therefore, is that, the concept of shortest move be parameterized.: that a move is analyzed as 'shortest' in a given language only after having compared the options and outputs of all other moves within the language L. Put differently, that every move termed 'shortest' is transderivationally dependent.

5.3 Spell-Out and Computational Issues

We have been able to establish in the fore-going chapters that prefixes and suffixes make up part of Lamnso' morphology. On minimalist assumptions, these prefixes and suffixes are part of the lexical resources contained in the Lamnso' lexicon. These lexical units are expected to be computed within the working area before spell-out; if such derivations are to converge at the interface levels. If any operations on the tree structures take place between spell-out and the interface levels, such derivations will not affect the mechanisms of derivations within the MP.

This study suggests that, the Chomskyan Operation Select will fail to compute Lamnso' nouns since this operation is not sensitive to class function. We recall from chapter one that within the Lamnso' noun class system, nouns that fall into particular classes take particular number distinctive prefixes or suffixes. Consider the data in (26) of chapter one, repeated below as (4):

4)

Class	Function	Function Marker
Cl. 1	Sing.	ϕ -
Cl. 1	Pl.	a-
Cl. 2	Sing.	- ϕ
Cl. 2	Pl.	-si
Cl. 3	Sing.	shi-
Cl. 3	Pl.	vi-
Cl. 4	Sing.	ki-
Cl. 4	Pl.	me-

In (4) every noun class carries either a prefix or a suffix nominal marker that functions as a singular or plural distinctive marker. On minimalist assumptions, the

computation of any Lamnso' noun must take the choice of the class function marker into consideration. In other words, if one computes a class 4 noun with the distinctive class function marker of class 3, such a noun crashes as in (5b) below:

- 5) a) **ki- kún**
 sing. N
 cl.4 cl. 4
- b) **vi- kún**
 pl. N
 cl. 4 cl. 4
- b) ***shi- kún**
 sing. N
 cl. 3 cl. 4
- b) ***me- kún**
 pl. N
 cl. 3 cl. 4

The lexical items in (5b) fail to converge because of the wrong choices made by Operation Select in its choices of lexical units towards nominal computation.

This study submits that Operation Select in Lamnso' must be made sensitive to class function. That the root of the noun is selected first, then Operation Select must only choose the function marker of an identical class from which the noun to be

computed is drawn. Failure to consider these will lead to derivations such as those in (5b) which are deviant structures in Lamnso' grammar.

The proposal of this study, is therefore that the Chomskyan Operation Select be parameterized and made sensitive to the idiosyncrasies of lexical and phrasal computations of languages. This operation as it is will derive structures that will be judged illegitimate at the interface levels given that the C-I interface in Lamnso' for example, must be sensitive to class function. It is only then that it can rule-out as an illegitimate lexical derivation as that in example (5b).

In like manner, we take into cognizance the articulated clause structure for Lamnso' in Chapter Three, and consider the syntactic word order in this clause, which necessitates that the head verb moves to adjoin with the head of ASP. We argue that TNS and ASP serve as the locus of lexical insertion, that the TNS marker being morphologically dependent on the subject NP necessitates that Operation Select be agreement conscious in its selection of the TNS marker; that unlike TNS, the ASP marker in Lamnso' has no morphological agreement relations with either the verb or any other constituent. ASP in Lamnso' behaves like a functional head.

As a consequence, Operation Select must not necessarily be sensitive to any clausal constituent in its selection from the pool of Lamnso' lexical units. We therefore claim that contrary to Chomsky (1995), the insertion of the aspectual features onto the verb in Lamnso' occurs outside the "working area" but within Lamnso' syntax and is guided by the confines of the Head-Head relation. Consider the partial representation of V-movement within the Lamnso' clause in (6) represented in (7):

- 6) **audu u yuiri ne bv̂əy**
 audu PST kill Asp+Imp goat
 'Audu killed a goat.'

7)

Given (7), we follow Halle and Marantz (1992) to submit that the operations in the derivation between spell-out and PF cum C-I are the same and obey the same principles as those operations in the working area of the computational system. Put differently, the computation of words in Lamnso' do not take place only within the computational system as Chomsky (1995) claims. Those computations within the syntax proper are also relevant in derivations within Lamnso' grammar. Such derivations do not affect the mechanisms of the working area within the MP.

We argue further that the derivation of the head of ASP" can afford to surface only at the syntax level of the computation of the Lamnso' clause. In addition, we claim that the head of ASP" obeys the economy principle of Procrastinate, the principle of laziness which demands that the laziest thing to do is to do nothing. In other words, since the Head of ASP" has no agreement relations with neither the verb nor the subject NP, it can simply surface after spell-out and will be computed within the syntax of Lamnso' proper yielding a well-formed derivation within Lamnso' clausal derivations.

5.4 Agreement Issues

We recall our postulation of L-features for the subject NP and phi-features for AGR in example (40) of Chapter Three represented in (8) below:

- 8) a) **me- n̄n me e yí sá_ e súp**
 Numb bird Numb TNS eat rice in farm

'The birds ate the rice in the farm'

- b) ***me- n̄n shi e yí sá_ e súp**
 Numb bird Numb TNS eat rice in farm.

Our claim in (8) is that the phi-features of AGR-S are employed to check the lexical features of the subject NP. Where agreement fails to hold between two head phrases, the derivation crashes. In like manner, person agreement is captured by the TNS marker which surfaces as the lengthened copy of the final vowel of the subject NP (see section 3.3.1).

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The Lamnso' noun class system and the lexical items that constitute the Lamnso' noun and its modifiers led us in Chapter Three to claim that agreement plays a major role within the working area of the Lamnso' nominal computation. We claimed that Operation Select and Operation Merge must be guided by number function and agreement respectively in the choice of lexical items selected for combination and in the computation of phrasal units, if the derivation is to converge in Lamnso' (see example (64) and (62) of Chapter Three). Operation Move, though motivated by the desire to check morphological features must ensure that the constituent in its landing site does not disrupt the interlocking agreement relations within the clause. In other words, the features of the moving constituent must be in agreement with those of the constituents that precede and/or follow it, given the syntactic order of constituents within the Lamnso' clause. V-movement postulated in Lamnso' grammar must have its V-features checked to guarantee that they agree with those of the constituents it adjoins to.

We therefore submit that all operations within the Working Area of Lamnso' grammar must be guided by agreement. That movement within the Lamnso' clause

is an agreement issue. We propose therefore that all computations in Lamnso' must of necessity take agreement into consideration. That Lamnso' grammar is agreement oriented.

Summary

In this chapter, we have attempted to evaluate the MP principles that govern well-formed structures in Lamnso'. The chapter examines movement issues and claims that the economy principle of Shortest Move, is not a global filter. In addition, the Chapter reveals that the Chomskyan Operation Select as it is, has the capability to generate ill-formed structures in Lamnso'. The chapter therefore suggests that Operation Select has to be made sensitive to class function to avoid the selection of wrong lexical units for combination. The C-I interface level of the Chomskyan 'machine' must also be sensitive to class function, if it is to function adequately. The chapter therefore proposes that Operation Select and the interface levels be parameterized to take care of language particular structures. The chapter discusses the issue of agreement and concludes that the computation of phrasal units in

Lamnso' must be agreement governed. The chapter advocates for an agreement oriented computation for Lamnso' grammar.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

In the last five chapters, we have attempted a systematic presentation of research findings on operative relations within the Lamnso' clause. The major goals of the study were:

- a) To evaluate the claims of the Minimalist Program in the light of Lamnso' grammar and the implications there-of for syntactic theory.
- b) To determine the basic relations both within and between the major components of the Lamnso' clause.
- c) To investigate the idiosyncrasies of movement structures in the Lamnso' clause and the effects of such movements on the agreement relations within the clause.

6.1 Findings of the Study

In this study, we have highlighted some important issues in Lamnso' syntax. We have for instance established that Lamnso' is a noun class language with elaborate concord markers. However, Lamnso' nouns unlike most Bantu noun class

languages does not exhibit class meaning. The Lamnso' noun class system has prefixes and limited suffixes which distinguish the singular plural function and trigger a chain of interlocking agreement relations within the Lamnso' clause. The study categorizes Lamnso' verbs into two groups: the simple verbs and the complex verbs. Complex verbs take extensional suffixes. These extensions and the internal structure of the Lamnso' verb have been accorded a critical analysis.

We have investigated the internal structures of the major components of the Lamnso' clause; and elaborately analyzed both the internal relations within each constituent and the operative relations between the components. Given our morphosyntactic approach to the study of derivations in Lamnso', this work has examined Lamnso' derivations in the light of the Minimalist conceptions. The computation of lexical items and each of the basic components of the Lamnso' clause has been examined. The Thesis examines in detail, movement structures within the Lamnso' clause. The language has been identified as a *wh-in-situ* language similar to Chinese and Japanese (Cheng, 1991). We have established that there is V-movement in Lamnso', similar to that which has been found to exist in the Kru languages (Koopman (1984), Tellier (1987)).

Given the basic relations between the Lamnso' subject NP and the INFL, this thesis adopts Pollock's (1989) conception of the INFL as 'split' and Chomsky's (1991, 1992) conception of AGR-S" and AGR-O". Our analysis reveals that Chomsky's (1991, 1992) universal clause structure fails to wholly accommodate the Lamnso' clause. This work therefore proposes a modified version of the clause structure for Lamnso'. Our articulated clause structure in example (74) of Chapter Three, represents the order of constituent stringing in the Lamnso' clausal derivations.

The implications of the study to linguistic theory are three fold. Firstly, given the prefixes and suffixes that are an integral part of the lexical resources in Lamnso', this work suggests that Operation Select of the Chomskyan computational system must be made sensitive to prefix and suffix function, if well-formed lexical outputs are to result from lexical computations in Lamnso'. The work also suggests that computations be ordered beginning with lexical items and graduating to phrases and then to clauses. Such a progressive consideration of computation in Lamnso' reveals our claim that Lamnso' syntax is a syntax of agreement.

In the same vein, the thesis has convincingly proven that, in the computation of phrasal structures in Lamnso', all operations within the Working Area of the Chomskyan Computational Machine must obligatorily be agreement governed else such derivations will crash at the interface levels. This level (the interface level), must therefore be made sensitive to both class function (for lexical computation) and agreement (for lexical, and clausal phrasal computation). What all these indicate, is that both the operations within the working area and the C-I interface level have to be parameterized to adequately compute derivations for languages like Lamnso' with given morphosyntactic characteristics that are derivationally obligatory. This thesis, therefore, subscribes to Amfani's (1997) "Syntax of Agreement".

Secondly, we have employed Lamnso' data to justify that the Economy Principle of Shortest Move fails as a global filter. Rather it can only function adequately given language particular specifications. This work, therefore proposes that shortest move be parameterized to accommodate language particular characteristics of movement structures.

Finally, the study proposes that Chomsky's (1991, 1992) universal clause structure be modified to reflect the structural idiosyncrasies of languages like Lamnso' whose constituent order exhibits given peculiarities.

6.2 Residual Problems

There exist a small group of nouns that belong to the basic vocabulary of Lamnso' but do not exhibit the identified morphological characteristics of the four noun classes in the language. Maybe a detailed phonological and historical study of such nouns can result in a better analysis of their peculiar morphological structures. This study has not found convincing evidence for the peculiar morphological characteristics of these nouns. The existence of words which are not controlled by class agreements and yet cannot be decomposed into roots and affixes have been referred to, within Bantu languages as Autonomous Particles. Such words are frequent in Swahili (Alexandre 1967).

The various noun class prefixes and suffixes trigger agreement relations both within the subject NP and across the Lamnso' clause. It is surprising that such morphological agreement relations do not feature (with and) within the Lamnso' VP,

as is the case for most Bantu noun class languages. In addition, the Lamnso' verbal system is complicated. It frequently displays confusing rudiments with no even structural features. This work has found it difficult to relate such features with fixed rules, to a set of hypothetical common roots. Our only suggestion is that Lamnso' might belong to the Bantu group of languages which Irvine (1957) refers to as the "Bantoid" languages, which he in turn describes as "... incomplete Bantu" which share remarkable features including the apparent lack of the typical Bantu nasal prefixes. Arnott (1970) has pointed out that Fula displays a verbal system very similar to what we have observed with Lamnso' VP. He points out that the verbal system of Fula is formerly differentiated, rather complex and characterized by a group of markers, suffixed to its extensions. A comparative study of this group (Lamnso', Kan and Kensense, etc.) in relation to its neighbours would probably throw a good deal of light on the classification of 'Bantoid' languages, and most probably their verbal system.. The characteristics of the Lamnso' nominal and verbal systems, seem to fit Irvine's description of this group.

We realize that there are no absolute answers: but we do believe that the process of thinking these questions through debating them and hazarding an

argument can be illuminating - and perhaps even enlightening. Therefore, there is no suggestion that this study represents an exhaustive study of operative relations in the Lamnso' clause; rather, it represents the beginning of research in the syntax of the language. Hopefully, this description of a corpus of Lamnso' data particularly with respect to the Minimalist Program of Chomskyan linguistics will contribute in one small way or the other to expanding an understanding of lexical, phrasal and clausal computation in such African class languages that are being subjected and analyzed within some of the most current grammatical theories in existence.

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APPENDIX I

LAMNSO' PRONOUNS

1) Independent Pronouns

mo	I
vér	we
vén	you (pl.)
à	you (sing.)
wu	he/she
áwune	they

2) Possessive Pronouns

Kém	mine
Kér	ours
ké	yours (sing.)
kén	yours (pl.)
kfa	his/her
kév	theirs

3) Object Pronouns

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mu	I
vèr	we
wò	you (sing.)
vén	you (pl.)
wún	he/she
áwune	they

4) Interrogative Pronouns

ká	what
lá	who (sing.)
alá	who (pl.)
kine	which (sing.)
vine	which (pl.)

5) Demonstratives

kin	this
vān	this
rān	this
vin	these
kisà	that
rāsà	that
visà	that
visà	those

APPENDIX II

The following data show that tone in Lamnso' is grammatical:

- 1) a) à/wò 'you'
 b) á/áwune 'they'

Consider 1(a) and (b) in the sentences below:

- i) à du ø é wáy a?
 you go Non-PST to market Q

'Are you going to the market?'

- ii) á du ø é wáy a?
 they go Non-PST to market Q

'Are they going to the market?'

- iii) mo o wiy fo lá' à a ló ne
 I PST come to home you PST leave Asp.(Perf)

'I came home when you had left.'

iv) mo o wiy fo lá' ²⁶¹ á a ló ne
 I PST come to home they PST leave Asp (Perf)
 'I came home when they had left..'

2) a)

kici ki i gbù
 tree Numb PST fell
 'The tree fell.'

b) biy e gbù fo kici.
 Kolanut PST fall from tree
 'Kolanut fell from the tree.'

3) a) wíri i gwar kov.
 People PST cut forest
 'People were cutting the forest.'

b) wiri i gwar vicí e kóv.
 People PST cut trees in forest
 'People were cutting trees in the forest.'

4) a) $\dot{r}\partial v$ $\emptyset$ 262 $kf\partial r$ $\underline{r\acute{e}}$.
 beetle Non-PST chew yam
 'The beetle is eating yam.'

b) $r\partial v$ $\emptyset$ $dz\grave{\partial}$ e $r\acute{e}$.
 beetle Non-PST is in yam
 'The beetle is in the yam.'

5) a) $\underline{sh\grave{a}\eta}$ $dz\grave{\partial}$ $kf\partial\grave{\partial}$ $kish\grave{a}$.
 chain is rope metal
 'The chain is a metal rope.'

b) wir $\emptyset$ $ts\grave{\partial}r$ $jw\acute{i}$ $\acute{e}$ $sh\grave{a}\eta$.
 person Non-PST tether dog with chain
 'Somebody has tethered a dog with a chain.'

The data in (2) to (5) reveal that, the object NP takes a high tone if it is preceded by a preposition. Notice that the same words do not take the high tone in any other syntactic environment or position in the clause.

APPENDIX III

VERBAL EXTENSIONS

a) The Suffix -nin

When -nin occurs as a suffix of any Lamnso' verb, it signals a state of affairs in which at least two parties are involved in a joint reciprocal action. Reciprocity in Lamnso' unlike in English-type languages can be signaled by a verbal affix. Such an extension constrains the verb to take more than one subject NP, eg:

i) **kila wúm lòn e [vpkuu-nin e wúy]**

kila and lòn PAST insult+Recip. in market

'Kila and Lòn insulted each other in the market.'

ii) **jwisi i lúm-nin e kùy.**

dogs PST bit+Recip. in fence

'The dogs bit each other in the fence.'

b) The Suffix -ri

When -ri occurs as a verbal extension, it encodes repeated action, i.e., the subject NP carrying out the action does it over and over. eg:

i) **kila a [vpkuu-ri 264 lòn]**

kila PST insult+Repetitive lòn

'Kila repeatedly insulted Lòn.'

kila a [vpkuu Lòn]

kila PST insult Lòn

'Kila insulted Lòn.'

ii) **ntasin e té-ri shinà.**

ntasin PST shoot+Repetitive bird

'Ntasin repeatedly shot a bird.'

ntasin e té shinà.

ntasin PST shoot bird

'Ntasin shot a bird.'

The verbs without the -ri extension state simply that the action denoted by the verb was carried out. It makes no reference as to how it was done.

c) The Suffix -kir

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This suffix encodes the iterative, i.e., an action that takes place intermittently, eg:

- i) **bvàysii lé'-kir fó súm.**
goats PST run+iterative from farm

'The goat intermittently ran (away) from the farm.'

- ii) **bvàysii lé' fó súm.**
goats PST run from farm

'The goats ran (away) from the farm.'

- iii) ***bvày e lé'kir fó súm**
goat PST run+iterative from farm

When the verb takes the iterative extension, it necessitates that the NP in subject position be in the plural form. In such instances, there is turn-taking in performing the action designated by the verb at intervals.

d) The Suffix -ir

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This is the causative suffix which arms the verb with the potency to assign case,

eg:

- i) lòn ɛ̃ [lém -ir kila]
 lòn PST wound+causative kila
 Lòn wounded Kila.'

- ii) lòn e [lém]
 lòn PST wound
 'Lòn was wounded.'

- iii) *lòn e [lém kila]
 lòn PST wound kila

e) The Suffix -si

The action designated by the verbs that take the -si extension must have been in progress for sometime. -si is added to specify that the agent of the clause simply completes or finalizes such an action, eg:

- i) yénla a rún-si ntòn medzòv.
 yénla PST full+completive pot water
 'Yénla completed filling the water pot.'

ii)

kila a rún-si

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kibàm

e

dzòv.

kila PST clean+completive

bag

in

water

'Kila rinsed the bag in the stream.'

APPENDIX IV

LOCATION OF BUI DIVISION IN THE NORTH WEST PROVINCE OF CAMEROON.

Source : Adapted from Hawkins and Brunt (1965)